

1 **Assessment of the eutrophication status at Mediterranean sub-basin scale, within the**
2 **European Marine Strategy Framework Directive**

3

4 Michele Giani ¹, Alexandra Pavlidou ^{*2a}, Martina Kralj ¹, Ioanna Varkitzi ^{2a}, Angel Borja ³, Iratxe
5 Menchaca ³, Marina Lipizer ¹, Elena Partescano ¹, Lidia Urbini ¹, Janja Francé ⁴, Erika Magaletti
6 ⁵, Alessandra Nguyen Xuan ⁵, Pasquale Lanera ⁵, Sanda Skejić ⁶, Damir Ivanković ⁶, Živana
7 Ninčević Gladan ⁶, Slavica Matijević ⁶, Maria Pantazi ^{2b}, Kalliopi Pagou ^{2a}

8

9 ¹OGS, National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics, Trieste, Italy

10 ^{2a} Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Institute of Oceanography, 46.7 Km Athens-Sounio
11 Ave, Mavro Lithari, Anavissos, Attika, Greece

12 ^{2b} Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Institute of Marine Biological Resources and Inland
13 Waters, HCMR, 576A Vouliagmenis Ave., 16452 Argyroupoli, Greece

14 ³AZTI, Marine Research; Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA); Pasaia, Spain

15 ⁴NIB, National Institute of Biology, Marine Biology Station Piran, Slovenia

16 ⁵ISPRA, Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale, Roma, Italy

17 ⁶IZOR, Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries, Split, Croatia

18

19 *Corresponding author: E-mail address: aleka@hcmr.gr (Alexandra Pavlidou).

20

21

22 **ABSTRACT**

23 The aim of this work is to define harmonized reference conditions and assessment thresholds
24 for selected criteria elements of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) Descriptor
25 5 (Eutrophication) in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea and to test if a tool for integrated
26 assessment of the status of marine systems can be used as a common methodological
27 approach. In this frame, we tested two statistical approaches in order to set threshold values
28 for four criteria of Descriptor 5: nutrients, chlorophyll a, transparency and dissolved oxygen in
29 the bottom waters. This is the first attempt to set common methods for the assessment of
30 eutrophication in the Eastern Mediterranean, which is essential in marine environments,
31 especially those shared by several countries. To this end, we have applied common criteria
32 and metrics and established thresholds “Good” and “Moderate” for nutrients, chlorophyll a,
33 transparency and dissolved oxygen in the bottom waters for the different Water Types of the
34 Adriatic and Aegean Seas (I, II, IIIW, IIIE), based on datasets provided by Italy, Slovenia, Croatia
35 and Greece. The selected criteria elements were common for all countries, providing a unified
36 approach to GES assessment of two case study areas: the Adriatic Sea and the Saronikos Gulf.
37 Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DIN) threshold values of 15.6, 6.85, 1.61 and 2.11 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ were
38 set for the Water Types I, II, IIIW and IIIE, respectively.

39 We also tested if an aggregation tool for GES assessment, such as Nested Environmental status
40 Assessment Tool (NEAT), could be used as a common methodological approach. The
41 comparison of NEAT with TRIX showed good comparability. In this end, NEAT can be used as
42 a useful and much needed assessment tool for assessing eutrophication status of the marine.
43 It is noteworthy that this work revealed the need to apply common procedures in data
44 treatment and assessment evaluation.

45 Keywords: MSFD, aggregation, thresholds, nutrients, chlorophyll, oxygen, transparency

46 1. INTRODUCTION

47 Eutrophication is one of the greatest threats to the health of estuarine, coastal and marine
48 ecosystems worldwide (Malone and Newton, 2020; United Nations, 2021; IOC-UNESCO,
49 2022). It is the result of a supply of nutrients into coastal and marine regions that exceeds the
50 ecological capacity of the ecosystem (Nixon, 2009). International and European regulations
51 have contributed to the mitigation of eutrophication problem, through programs
52 implemented by regional conventions such as the Oslo-Paris Convention for the Protection of
53 the Northeast Atlantic (OSPAR), the Helsinki Convention (HELCOM) for the Protection of the
54 Baltic Sea, the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal
55 Region of the Mediterranean (Barcelona Convention, 1995) and, the Bucharest Convention
56 for the Black Sea. Also, in the European Union (EU), several legislative instruments have been
57 approved, such as the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD (91/271/EEC)) and
58 Nitrates Directive (ND, (91/676/EEC), whilst in the United States (US) the Clean Water Act (PL
59 92–500, 1972) and Coastal Zone Management Act (PL 92–583, 1972) are the main
60 instruments. EU has also set two major legal frameworks to assess and protect the quality of
61 marine waters: the Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC), and the Marine Strategy
62 Framework Directive (MSFD; 2008/56/EC). Under the MSFD, assessment of descriptor 5
63 (*Human-induced eutrophication is minimized, especially adverse effects thereof, such as losses*
64 *in biodiversity, ecosystem degradation, harmful algae blooms and oxygen deficiency in bottom*
65 *waters*) includes eight criteria elements (Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848; Patricio et al.,
66 2016). To assess the status of these criteria, we need to set reference conditions (i.e., values
67 for the best and the worst environmental status), target values (boundary between good and
68 non-good status), and thresholds for the remaining quality classes (Borja et al., 2011; 2012).
69 To our knowledge, works for the definition of the boundaries between “good” and “not -
70 good” status at a regional level are very few. There are some for coastal fish (Laurila-Pant et
71 al., 2021), sea-floor integrity (Hiddink et al., 2023) or litter (van Loon et al., 2019; Werner et
72 al., 2020), and some criteria can be seen in Vasilakopoulos et al. (2022). Target values for
73 nutrients have been defined in the Black Sea (Bulgarian side; Doncheva et al., 2018), and in
74 the Portuguese continental EEZ (Cabrita et al., 2015), however, they are still lacking for the
75 Eastern Mediterranean Sea. In this end, various methods have been developed and tested in
76 the EU to assess eutrophication under European Directives (e.g. Ferreira et al., 2011; Cabrita
77 et al., 2015; Andersen et al., 2017; Wasmund et al., 2017; Pavlidou et al., 2019; Borja et al.,
78 2019). However, in many cases, these methods give different assessment results in terms of
79 quality classes, when they are applied to the same area. This indicates the need to agree and

80 to adopt common methodologies, at least at regional or sub-regional level. It is noteworthy,
81 that common methodologies and methodological standards for eutrophication assessment
82 are still lacking at the Mediterranean scale (Pavlidou et al., 2015; Varkitzi et al., 2018) and
83 Mediterranean countries use many different approaches for Good Environmental Status (GES)
84 assessment (Ferreira et al., 2011). Specifically, for the GES evaluation in marine environments
85 which are shared by many countries, such as the Adriatic Sea and the Levantine – Aegean
86 subregions, common criteria and metrics should be used by all countries involved, to ensure
87 comparability. Integrative tools such as the Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool
88 (NEAT; Borja et al., 2016) has been used at international level in different geographical areas
89 such as in the Southern Black Sea (Tan et al., 2023), in Biscay Bay (Menchaca et al., 2022), in
90 Malta’s marine waters (Borja et al., 2021), in the North-East Atlantic Ocean deep-sea
91 ecosystems (Kazanidis et al., 2020), in the Caspian Sea (Nemati et al., 2017), etc. Moreover,
92 modeling and other approaches have been recently used for setting threshold and reference
93 values in order to assess the quality of the marine environment (e.g. Van Leeuwen et al., 2023;
94 Hyttiäinen et al., 2024).

95 Taking this into account, the objectives of this work are: i) to define the harmonized reference
96 condition and assessment thresholds for selected criteria elements of MSFD Descriptor 5 (D5)
97 in the Eastern Mediterranean Sea, and ii) to test if an aggregation tool for GES assessment,
98 such as the NEAT can be used as a common methodological approach derived from the
99 comparison of national approaches. With this in mind, this work aims at answering the
100 following questions: (i) What are the gaps for the identification of eutrophication thresholds
101 and reference values? (ii) Is the application of a tool that allows an integrated assessment of
102 the status of marine system possible in the Eastern Mediterranean basin? (iii) Do the Eastern
103 Mediterranean countries, especially those sharing the same marine area, use common
104 methodologies for measuring the eutrophication criteria elements? (iv) How effective is the
105 application of the integrative tool in relation to the pressures and to other methodological
106 tools already in use in the study areas?

107 **2. METHODOLOGY**

108 **2.1. Description of case studies in the Adriatic Sea and Aegean-Levantine Sea subregions**

109 The entire Adriatic Sea and Saronikos Gulf (part of the Aegean Sea) were selected as different
110 case studies to test the methodological approaches for GES assessment in the context of D5,
111 given the availability of sufficient spatial and temporal coverage of the data, and the significant
112 anthropogenic pressures that affect the selected areas.

113 In the case of the Adriatic Sea, data from almost the entire coastal zone were used (Fig. 1a).
114 The Adriatic Sea (138,600 km²) reveals a north – south gradient of different oceanographic
115 and ecological features, characterized by highly variable conditions of the trophic state of
116 pelagic ecosystems (Polimene et al., 2006). The northern Adriatic Sea is among the most
117 productive areas in the Mediterranean Sea, although it recently experienced a decrement in
118 nutrient loads with subsequent reduction of chlorophyll a (Chl-a) concentrations and
119 productivity (Pugnetti et al., 2005; Giani et al., 2018; Viaroli et al., 2018; Brush et al., 2021).
120 The western part of the basin is eutrophic due to inputs from the Italian rivers, particularly the
121 Po River, while the eastern part is generally oligotrophic. The central and southern regions of
122 the Adriatic Sea are characterized by low primary productivity, with continental inputs of
123 minor importance in comparison to the northern Adriatic basin (Fonda Umani, 1996; Pugnetti
124 et al., 2005; Mangoni et al., 2017). Three distinct sub-areas have been considered in this study:
125 Northern Adriatic, Middle Adriatic and Southern Adriatic Sea (Figure 1a).

126 In the case of the Aegean Sea, data from the Saronikos Gulf were used. The Saronikos Gulf
127 (2.974 km²) is located on the western edge of the central Aegean Plateau, near the city of
128 Athens (Figure 1b). The Inner Saronikos Gulf at the northern part of the eastern basin receives
129 the treated wastewaters of ~5 million people (Pavlidou et al., 2019) from the second largest
130 Waste Water Treatment Plant (WWTP) in Europe. The treated sewage effluent is dispersed
131 into the Inner Gulf to the south, southeast and southwest of Psittalia island, according to the
132 prevailing circulation (Kontoyiannis, 2010) below the pycnocline or in the surface layer during
133 the cold period (December-April), when the water column is homogenized (Simboura et al.,
134 2005; Pavlidou et al., 2015). Industrial and shipping activities affect the environmental quality
135 of the gulf, especially in Elefsis Bay, a small and shallow embayment (71.48 km²; 33 m), almost
136 enclosed, which is connected to the Saronikos Gulf by two narrow and shallow channels.
137 Elefsis Bay is differentiated from the Saronikos Gulf not only in its morphology, but also in the
138 extent of the pollution it receives. The physical setting of the Elefsis Bay with low freshwater
139 inflows and limited water exchange, leads to a strong seasonal density stratification of the
140 water mass resulting in hypoxia and anoxia that lasts for about five months. These conditions
141 retain nutrients and organic matter within the bay and lead to high nutrient accumulation
142 (Pavlidou et al., 2013).

143

144 Figure 1: (a) Monitoring stations (corresponding to smallest Spatial Assessment Units) in the
 145 Adriatic Sea considered in the case study (red dots) and geographical boundaries between the
 146 three distinct subdivisions: Northern Adriatic, Middle Adriatic and Southern Adriatic. (b)
 147 Monitoring stations in the Saronikos Gulf (S-stations) and Spatial Assessment Units (with
 148 different colors) used for the application of NEAT assessment tool to the Saronikos Gulf case
 149 study.

150

151 **2.2 Criteria selected, threshold values (Good / Moderate boundaries) and reference / worst**
 152 **conditions.**

153 The following definitions are to be considered for the purposes of the present paper:

- 154 ● ‘Criteria Elements’: means constituent elements of an ecosystem, particularly its
 155 biological elements (species, habitats and their communities), or aspects of pressures
 156 on the marine environment which are assessed under each criterion (EU, 2017a);
- 157 ● ‘Ecological quality ratio (EQR)’: - the ration between the value of the observed
 158 biological parameter for a given surface water body and the expected value under
 159 reference conditions, expressed as a numerical value between 0 and 1, with high
 160 ecological status represented by values close to one and bad ecological status by
 161 values close to zero (European Commission, 2003);
- 162 ● ‘Threshold Value’: a value or range of values that allow for an assessment of the
 163 quality level achieved for a particular criterion, thereby contributing to the
 164 assessment of the extent to which GES is being achieved (EU, 2017a);

- 165 ● 'Target Value': the boundary value between good and non-good status used in NEAT
166 (Borja et al., 2019);
- 167 ● 'Reference Conditions' and 'Worst Conditions': values to assess the environmental
168 status for each criterion element for each water type. Reference condition refers to a
169 condition with no or minimal disturbance by anthropogenic activities, worst condition
170 refers to the highest impact due to anthropogenic disturbances for each water type.

171 We used official data of the period 2010-2018 from national Competent Authorities for the
172 environmental assessment, and data from the Mediterranean Sea - Eutrophication and Acidity
173 aggregated datasets (EMODnet Chemistry, 2021) provided by the European Marine
174 Observation and Data Network for Chemistry (EMODnet), for setting reference conditions and
175 target values. Only stations with a minimum of four samplings per year distributed in four
176 seasons (Jan-Feb-Mar; Apr-May-Jun; Jul-Aug-Sep; Oct-Nov-Dec) were considered for the
177 following analysis, and at least one sampling in each season was considered necessary for each
178 station. Only stations for which temperature, salinity, Chl-a, dissolved oxygen in bottom
179 waters and nutrients were simultaneously available, were selected. Furthermore, for
180 thresholds setting, for the Water Types (WT) I and II (Table S1; Supplementary Material), the
181 data set was enlarged with the coastal data provided by Regional Agency for Prevention,
182 Environment and Energy Emilia Romagna for the period 2010-2019 in order investigate the
183 statistical relationships between variables.

184 All data were evaluated. A detailed description of the data evaluation is included in the
185 supplementary material. Data available for this case study and concentrations ranges are
186 shown in Table 1. In total, 70 stations were used in the Adriatic Sea and 11 stations in the
187 Saronikos Gulf, totalizing 81 (Figure 1).

188 MSFD eutrophication criteria were used in this work (Ferreira et al., 2011; MSFD Commission
189 Decision (EU) 2017/848). These were: concentrations of Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DIN:
190 nitrate - NO_3 + nitrite - NO_2 + ammonium - NH_4), Total Nitrogen (TN), Dissolved Inorganic
191 Phosphorus (PO_4), Total Phosphorus (TP), all representing MSFD criterion D5C1, and
192 chlorophyll-a (criterion D5C2). Further, the near bottom oxygen concentrations were used,
193 representing MSFD criterion D5C5 and water transparency, expressed as Secchi disk depth
194 (criterion D5C4) (Table 2). The criteria selected in this work were common for all countries in
195 the pilot area (Italy, Slovenia, Croatia, Greece), providing a unified approach to GES
196 assessment of the case studies. These criteria were analogous to those used to assess
197 eutrophication status in the Baltic Sea (HELCOM, 2018; Murray et al., 2019), except in the case

198 of Adriatic Sea, where TP was preferred over dissolved inorganic phosphorus (PO₄) as 25% of
 199 surface PO₄ concentrations were below the limit of detection (LOD) of the method used (Table
 200 S2). PO₄ concentrations were used only in the case of the Saronikos Gulf. It has to be outlined
 201 that the LOD for the determination of the PO₄ and TP concentrations provided by some
 202 laboratories (Table S2) were elevated (0.10-0.16 μmol L⁻¹), especially considering that the
 203 surface waters of the eastern Mediterranean Sea are characterized by quite low PO₄ and TP
 204 concentrations. Average concentrations in summer range from 0.04 to 0.09 μmol L⁻¹ for the
 205 southern and northern Adriatic Sea, respectively (Zavatarelli et al., 1998, Grilli et al., 2020)
 206 whereas the average winter concentrations in the surface layer (0-50 m) are, according to
 207 Lazzari et al. (2016), 0.02 μmol L⁻¹ both in the Adriatic and Aegean Seas.

208 Table 1: Summary of parameters and their ranges for Italian, Slovenian, Croatian and Greek
 209 datasets for the period 2010-2018. LOD: limit of detection. LODs are reported in Table S2.

	Italy	Slovenia	Croatia	Greece
N. of stations	48	6	16	11
Years	2015-2017	2011-2017	2012-2018	2010-2017
Temperature (°C)	5.1-29.6	4.5-27.4	8.1-28.6	10.3-28.9
Salinity	10.3-39.2	27.5-38.5	9.6-39.1	37.3-28.9
Transparency -Secchi disk depth (m)	0.5-30.0	0.5-18.0	5.9-25.3	5.7 - 14.9
Bottom Dissolved Oxygen (μmol L ⁻¹)	27-324	50-324	117-307	0.0-285
Nitrate NO ₃ (μmol L ⁻¹)	<LOD-119	<LOD-62.5	<LOD-69.2	<LOD-11.1
Nitrite NO ₂ (μmol L ⁻¹)	<LOD-4.40	<LOD-1.85	<LOD-3.50	<LOD-2.52
Phosphate PO ₄ (μmol L ⁻¹)	<LOD-1.13	<LOD-1.40	<LOD-0.50	<LOD-5.06
Silicate Si(OH) ₄ (μmol L ⁻¹)	<LOD-67.2	<LOD-20.6	<LOD-17.4	0.15-72.2
Ammonium NH ₄ (μmol L ⁻¹)	<LOD-10.9	<LOD-40.9	<LOD-7.50	<LOD-26.6
Total Nitrogen (μmol L ⁻¹)	1.0-123	8.30-120	1.60-44.0	2.68-46.9
Total Phosphorus (μmol L ⁻¹)	<LOD-2.90	0.11-1.56	<LOD-1.80	0.02-5.92
Chlorophyll a (μg L ⁻¹)	0.01-27.5	0.10-10.9	0.02-6.90	LOD-9.19

210

211 In this study, the already defined Water Types I, II A, and III W (hereafter WT I, WT II and WT
 212 III) and WT III E, for coastal waters within WFD, have been adopted (WFD; European
 213 Commission, 2000; 2009; Giovanardi et al., 2018; see Supplementary Material, Table S1).
 214 Reference conditions and threshold values were defined for each of the WTs. This is a first
 215 step required to adopt a common approach towards the definition of reference conditions

216 and threshold values needed to discriminate different environmental status, for each of the
217 WTs. In the Saronikos Gulf, reference conditions, threshold values setting, and classification
218 criterion were derived only for WT IIIE, which, according to annual mean surface salinity (38.1),
219 is the only water type present in the area (Table S1). For the Adriatic Sea, Chl-a reference
220 values for WT I and WT IIA were obtained from Giovanardi et al. (2018). For DIN, TP and DO,
221 the reference values were derived as median values from a large dataset for the offshore
222 waters of the Adriatic Sea available through EMODnet Chemistry (HCMR/HNODC, 2021). The
223 same approach and dataset were also used to derive reference concentrations for WT III W,
224 as there was no reference for this WT in Giovanardi et al. (2018). The worst state for the three
225 WTs for each sub-area of the Adriatic Sea was derived from the highest concentration value
226 for Chl-a, DIN, TP and the lowest for DO. In a few cases, where the number of data was quite
227 limited, the range was extended considering the data available in the literature. For
228 transparency, references were selected from eutrophication data reported by Justic et al.
229 (1988), for WT I and WT IIA (years 1911-1913), and by Buljan and Zore-Armanda (1979), for
230 WT IIIW (years 1962-1965) (Tables 2 and 3).

231 The worst conditions in Saronikos Gulf (WT IIIE) were derived from the highest concentration
232 values for Chl-a, DIN, TP, PO₄ and the lowest for DO. Reference conditions for Chl-a (0.2 µg L⁻¹)
233 were derived from the WFD Mediterranean Intercalibration Exercise (MEDGIG) and refer to
234 the 90th percentile of depth integrated Chl-a concentrations (European Commission, 2018).
235 For DIN, TP, PO₄ reference values were derived from the lowest concentration value and for
236 DO from the highest, as annual averages of the mean integrated concentrations, from the
237 Saronikos Gulf large dataset available through EMODnet Chemistry (HCMR/HNODC, 2021).

238 Different methodological approaches were used to define threshold values needed for the
239 GES evaluation in the different water types, and two different methodological approaches
240 (NEAT and TRIX) were compared for D5 GES assessment.

241 Table 2: Criteria for descriptor D5 considered in the case studies together with the threshold values between Good/Moderate (G/M) Ecological Status
 242 in each EU Country: GR – Greece; CR – Croatia; SL – Slovenia; IT - Italy, that were used for previous reporting cycle of MSFD Art. 8 and 9.

Criteria		Criteria Elements	Abbreviation	Units	Threshold values			
					GR	CR	SL	IT
DC51 Nutrients in the water column	Primary	Total phosphorus concentration	TP	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$		0.6 ^c	0.42 ^d	
		Total nitrogen concentration	TN	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$				
		Dissolved inorganic nitrogen concentration	DIN	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$		15 ^c		
		Nitrate concentration	NO ₃		1 ^a		2.5 ^d	
		Phosphate (only for water type IIE in this study)	PO ₄	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	0.1 ^a	0.25 ^c	0.15 ^d	
D5C2 Chlorophyll-a in the water column	Primary	Chlorophyll -a concentration	Chl-a	$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	0.53 ^b	1.5 ^d	1.5 ^d	1.5 ^d
D5C4 Transparency	Secondary	Secchi disk depth	SD	m				
D5C5 Dissolved Oxygen in the bottom of the water column	Primary	Dissolved oxygen concentrations	DO	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$		3 mg L ⁻¹ _c		

243 ^aToolkit by Phillips et al. (2018); ^b 90th percentile; ^c 50th percentile; ^d geometric mean

244 Table 3: Metrics used for each criterion element, within Descriptor 5, in order to set threshold
 245 values for the indicators used. WT: Water Type.

Criteria	D5C1 Nutrients in the Water Column			D5C2 Chlorophyll-a	D5C4 Transparency	D5C5 Dissolved Oxygen in bottom water
Criteria Elements	DIN	TP	PO ₄	Chl a	Secchi Disk	DO
Metrics	Geometric mean for WT I, IIA, IIIW and arithmetic mean for WT IIIE	Geometric mean for WT I, IIA, IIIW and arithmetic mean for WT IIIE	Geometric mean for WT I, IIA, IIIW and arithmetic mean for WT IIIE	Geometric mean for WT I, IIA, IIIW and arithmetic mean for WT IIIE	Geometric mean for WT I, IIA, IIIW and arithmetic mean for WT IIIE	10 th percentile
Units	μmol L ⁻¹	μmol L ⁻¹	μmol L ⁻¹	μg L ⁻¹	M	μmol L ⁻¹
Water depth	Surface data for WT I, IIA, IIIW and water column for WT IIIE	Surface data for WT I, IIA, IIIW and water column for WT IIIE	Surface data for WT I, IIA, IIIW and water column for WT IIIE	Surface data for WT I, IIA, IIIW and water column for WT IIIE	Water column	Bottom water
Assessment period	Annual	Annual	Annual	Annual	Annual	June - November

246

247 For setting nutrient target values we evaluated the functional relationships between Chl-a and
 248 nutrients. This was done according to the statistical toolkit by Phillips et al. (2018) or, in the
 249 case of absence of relationships between DIN and Chl-a, based on linear regression between
 250 DIN and TP. This toolkit facilitates the application of the different statistical approaches
 251 proposed to establish the nutrient targets expressing the pressure-response relationships
 252 found between nutrients and phytoplankton in transitional and coastal waters (Salas Herrero
 253 et al., 2019). The toolkit allows the following types of regression models to be fitted: a) Type I
 254 regression: Model 1 (Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression of Chl-a Ecological Quality Ratio
 255 (EQR_{Chl-a}) versus nutrient concentration), assuming that uncertainty is in the calculation of
 256 EQR_{Chl-a} , which can lead to an underestimation of the slope, and Model 2 (Ordinary Least Squares
 257 (OLS) regression of nutrient concentration versus EQR_{Chl-a}), assuming that uncertainty is in the
 258 measurement of nutrient concentration, which can lead to an overestimation of the slope,
 259 and b) Type II Regression: Model 3 (Standardized Major Axis) and Model 4 (Ranged Major
 260 Axis), assuming equal uncertainty in measurement of both EQR_{Chl-a} and nutrient
 261 concentration. Since the significance of the slope of the geometric mean regression cannot be
 262 tested, the toolkit suggests that an $r^2 > 0.36$ is required, but when a type II ranged major axis

263 regression is used, this rule can be relaxed. Ranged major axis is a modification of major axis
264 regression in which the regression is performed on variables that are pre-standardized by their
265 ranges, and the resulting parameters are then returned on their original scales. Herein, we
266 used a type II regression (Ranged Major Axis, Model 4), a least squares regression where
267 EQR_{Chl-a} is the dependent (y) variable and nutrient concentration is the independent (x)
268 variable. This model accounts for uncertainty in the predictor variable (nutrients) and the
269 response variable (EQR_{Chl-a}) and primarily describes the first major axis by a bivariate normal
270 distribution.

271 As an alternative approach to linear regression, in particular for dissolved oxygen, we
272 calculated the cumulative probability curves and by comparing the curves of the different
273 water types, the 10-percentile was selected. This approach is based on the lower and upper
274 boundary values of the area under the curve of the related Probability Density Functions (PDF)
275 obtained from Johnson's distributions, according to Giovanardi et al. (2006). Johnson (1949)
276 described a system of frequency curves that represents transformations of the standard
277 normal curve. By applying these transformations to a standard normal variable, a wide variety
278 of non-normal distributions can be approximated, including distributions which are bounded
279 on either one or both sides. The main statistical characteristics of the Johnson distributions
280 are provided by means of:

- 281 ● central tendency measures: mean, median and mode
- 282 ● dispersion measures: STD, variance
- 283 ● moments of higher order: skewness, kurtosis
- 284 ● lambda (λ) and csi (ξ) parameters, representing simple scale and location factors
- 285 ● gamma (γ) and delta (δ) parameters, determining the shape of the distributions
- 286 ● type of distribution: SN (normal), SL (log-normal), SU (unbounded) or SB (bounded).

287 This family of distributions is capable of matching any combination of mean, SD, skewness and
288 kurtosis. Once a particular Johnson curve has been fitted, the normal integral was used to
289 compute the expected percentage points under the respective curve. This methodology was
290 implemented on data concerning nutrients and dissolved oxygen in the bottom waters. For
291 dissolved oxygen in the bottom waters, the period for the assessment was restricted to the
292 stratified period, from June to November (Table 3). All calculations were computed by means
293 of R (version R 4.0.4) with the package `suppDists` (Bob Wheeler, 2020).

294

295

296 **2.3 Integrated GES assessment**

297 As an integrated GES assessment method, we used the holistic NEAT (version 1.4) developed
298 for the integrated assessment of the status of marine waters within the European project
299 DEVOTES (Borja et al., 2016). This method has already been successfully used in different areas
300 of the Mediterranean Sea, such as the waters around Malta (Borja et al., 2021), the Saronikos
301 Gulf in the Aegean Sea (Pavlidou et al., 2019), or the whole Mediterranean and its sub-basins
302 (Borja et al., 2019), as well as the Black Sea (Tan et al., 2023). The whole dataset as reported
303 in Table 1 was used for the assessment of the Saronikos Gulf, while for the assessment of the
304 Adriatic Sea only surface layer data were used. The central principle of NEAT is its hierarchical
305 and nested structure of the environmental status of a given area, or Spatial Assessment Unit
306 (SAU), that is, information belonging to a SAU contributes to the specific assessment of this
307 SAU, as well as to the assessment of any other larger SAU that encompasses it, and therefore,
308 to the overall assessment. Considering this principle, NEAT architecture for the Adriatic Pilot
309 study is represented in Figure 2. The smallest SAUs were defined as squares of about 20 km²
310 in which at least 1 monitoring station was located, similarly to the extension used by Lefebvre
311 and Devreker (2020) for French coastal waters. These SAUs were then hierarchically grouped
312 in the western and eastern Northern Adriatic, in the western and eastern Middle Adriatic and
313 in the western Southern Adriatic Sea. The definition of SAUs representing small areas was
314 necessary due to the scarce spatial coverage of the stations (see Figure 1a), which does not
315 allow an interpolation. Moreover, contiguous stations could belong to different water types,
316 thus characterized by different boundaries and ranges for the criteria used in the GES
317 evaluation. The SAUs can be weighted by their surface area in the default mode of NEAT (Borja
318 et al., 2016). The outcomes of the aggregation are visualized into a number (NEAT value) and
319 a color, which corresponds to the status (i.e. high, good, moderate, poor and bad). These
320 quality classes are similar to those under the WFD. However, for the use in the MSFD, they
321 can be combined as GES (high-good) and not-GES (moderate-poor-bad). This NEAT value is
322 obtained for the whole assessed area but can be visualized in different forms. Each NEAT value
323 is accompanied by a quantitative estimate of the confidence of the result. This estimate is
324 calculated using the standard error (entered at the same time as the indicator value), and
325 performance of Monte Carlo simulations, to understand how this error propagates
326 throughout the assessment.

327

328 Figure 2: Nested hierarchies of pre-defined Spatial Assessment Units (SAUs) for the application
 329 of the Nested Environmental Assessment Tool (NEAT) to the Adriatic Sea case study. The
 330 aggregation level for the SAUs is indicated by the numbers in the right column.

331 For Saronikos Gulf, three SAUs were defined: Psittalia sewage outfall, Inner Gulf, and Elefsis
 332 Bay (Figure 1b). The smallest SAU is Psittalia (64.96 km²), whereas Elefsis bay and the Inner
 333 Saronikos Gulf covers an area of 71.49 km² and 417 km², respectively.

334 For the NEAT application, reference and worst conditions as well as target values
 335 (Good/Moderate boundaries; see target value definition above) for each criteria element is
 336 needed.

337

338 3. Results and discussion

339 3.1. Threshold values (Good/Moderate boundaries)

340 According to the first methodological approach, different types of linear regressions were run
 341 for each water type between the EQRs of Chl-a (EQR_{Chl-a}) and DIN, TP and PO₄. Significant
 342 regressions with R² around 0.50 were obtained for WT I and WT IIA between EQR_{Chl-a} and DIN,
 343 and EQR_{Chl-a} and TP (Table 4). For WT IIIW, such statistical analysis resulted in weak and/or no-
 344 significant relationships. For WT IIIE, the regressions were significant, but with weaker R²
 345 (lower than 0.36, which is considered as a lower limit for an adequate regression by Phillips et
 346 al. (2018)) (Table 4). The Good/Moderate values derived for TP, PO₄ and DIN resulting from
 347 this methodological approach for WT I, IIA and III are shown in Table 4.

348 Table 4: Results from different regression types between EQR_{Chl-a} (Ecological Quality Ratio)
 349 and nutrients, and the derived Good/Moderate (G/M) thresholds for different water types

350 (WT). DIN=Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen; TP=Total Phosphorus; N= number of data;
 351 OLS=Ordinary least square, SMA=Standardized Major Axis, RMA=Ranged Major Axis. NS: not
 352 significant

Water Type	Regressors	Regression results				Derived G/M thresholds ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)				
		N	R	R ²	p	Model 1 OLS (EQR _{Chl-a} on NUT)	Model 2 OLS (Nut on EQR _{Chl-a})	Model 3 SMA	Model 4 RMA	Removed Outliers N
WT I	EQR _{Chl-a} vs TP	79	-0.702	0.493	<0.001	0.71	0.63	0.66	0.66	1
	EQR _{Chl-a} vs DIN	74	-0.707	0.500	<0.001	16.4	14.2	15.1	15.6	3
WT IIA	EQR _{Chl-a} vs TP	39	-0.737	0.543	<0.001	0.48	0.34	0.40	0.42	5
	EQR _{Chl-a} vs DIN	44	-0.704	0.495	<0.001	9.33	4.51	6.09	6.85	1
WT IIIW	EQR _{Chl-a} vs TP	17	-0.099	0.010	NS					
	EQR _{Chl-a} vs DIN	17	-0.111	0.012	NS					
WT III E	EQR _{Chl-a} vs TP	173	-0.59	0.35	<0.001	0.33	0.24	0.27	0.28	3
	EQR _{Chl-a} vs DIN	173	-0.32	0.10	<0.001	2.11	1.02	1.21	1.44	4
	EQR _{Chl-a} vs PO ₄	173	-0.40	0.16	<0.001	0.10	0.05	0.06	0.07	4

353

354 The alternative methodological approach, based on cumulative probability curves of data
 355 obtained from Johnson distributions, was performed with data of Chl-a, DIN, TP and PO₄ (PO₄
 356 for Saronikos case study), dissolved oxygen in bottom waters, and Secchi disk depth. The main
 357 statistical characteristics of the Johnson distributions for each variable with their associated
 358 parameters are listed in Table 5.

359 The graphical representation of the frequency classes and the corresponding probability
 360 density function (PDF) for different variables (Figures 3 and 4) provide a comprehensive
 361 description of the associated statistical distributions, with a different range of variation and
 362 associated probability attributed to each water type.

363 Values corresponding to different quantiles of the area under the curve of the PDF obtained
 364 from Johnson distributions were calculated (Table 6) and the cumulative probability plots
 365 were constructed (Figures 5 and 6). In some cases, the presented quantiles were used to
 366 derive threshold values.

367 Table 5: Distribution type and main statistical parameters of the Johnson distributions of the criteria elements. Distribution types: SB - bounded Johnson
 368 distribution, SL – lognormal (semi-bounded) Johnson distribution, SU - unbounded Johnson distribution, STD Standard Deviation, Var- Variance, Sk-Skewness,
 369 WT-Water Type.

370

Variables	Units	Water Type	Type	Gamma (γ)	Delta (δ)	Csi (ξ)	Lambda (λ)	Mean	Median	Mode	Var	STD	Pearson Sk	Skewness	Kurtosis
Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	WT I	SB	0.59	0.38	-0.43	52.41	15.8	8.74	-0.42	279.1	16.71	0.97	0.815	-0.75
		WT IIA	SB	2.12	0.86	-0.12	32.14	3.61	2.36	0.52	13.75	3.71	0.83	1.938	4.35
		WT IIIW	SU	-1.30	1.16	0.63	0.79	2.17	1.69	1.24	3.62	1.90	0.49	-3.748	36.74
		WT III E	SB	1.654	0.652	0.077	8.638	1.25	0.71	0.14	1.90	1.38	0.80	1.94	3.79
Total Phosphorus	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	WT I	SB	1.10	0.95	0.00	1.70	0.47	0.41	0.21	0.09	0.31	0.86	0.839	0.08
		WT II	SU	-0.62	0.65	0.18	0.04	0.33	0.22	0.17	0.32	0.57	0.29	-37.777	15512
		WT IIIW	SL	0.00	0.77	0.12	0.12	0.40	0.24	0.14	0.34	0.58	0.44	15.310	1201
		WT III E	SL	0.00	1.593	-0.003	0.136	0.16	0.13	0.09	0.01	0.12	0.64	2.42	11.96
Dissolved Oxygen Bottom	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	WT I	SB	-0.39	0.97	45	261	197	201	226	2922	54.06	-0.54	-0.260	-0.79
		WT IIA	SU	0.76	1.66	261	52	232	236	244	1805	42.49	-0.29	-1.088	4.40
		WT IIIW	SL	0.00	5.81	104	133	239	237	233	546	23.38	0.25	0.525	0.49
		WT III E	SU	0.553	0.522	221	5.6	177	214	211	99.4	315	-0.108	-246	2383
Secchi disk	m	WT I	SB	1.75	0.99	0.55	21.10	4.42	3.61	1.88	8.61	2.93	0.86	1.311	1.595
		WT IIA	SL	0.00	2.86	-3.25	10.28	7.68	7.03	5.85	15.54	3.94	0.46	1.129	2.350
		WT IIIW	SB	0.11	0.96	0.60	30.57	15.13	15.00	14.09	42.20	6.50	0.16	0.10	-0.89
		WT III E	SB	0.37	1.07	-1.81	28.21	10.22	9.87	8.14	30.10	5.48	0.38	0.25	-0.73
Phosphate	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	WT III E	SU	-1.032	0.669	0.018	0.009	0.08	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.19	0.28	-32.36	9.394
Chl a	$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	WT I	SU	-1.33	0.66	0.26	0.22	2.91	1.09	0.87	66.67	8.17	0.25	-36.455	12809
		WT IIA	SB	3.73	1.17	0.00	12.47	0.67	0.50	0.26	0.32	0.56	0.73	2.137	6.35
		WT IIIW	SL	0.00	1.52	-0.02	0.17	0.19	0.15	0.09	0.02	0.15	0.65	2.60	14.02
		WT III E	SB	4.17	0.82	0.05	37.80	0.50	0.27	0.11	0.50	0.67	0.57	4.12	24.48

371

373

374 Figure 3: Frequency classes of nutrients, dissolved oxygen in bottom waters, Chlorophyll a and
 375 Secchi disk depth with corresponding Probability Density Functions (red) obtained from
 376 Johnson distributions for the Adriatic Sea case study.

377

378

379 Figure 4: Frequency classes of nutrients, dissolved oxygen in bottom waters, Chlorophyll a and
 380 Secchi disk depth with corresponding Probability Density Functions (red) obtained from
 381 Johnson distributions for the Saronikos Gulf case study.

382 Threshold values or boundaries between G/M status (i.e. between GES and non-GES status)
 383 for D5C2 Chl-a were based on the work of the WFD Mediterranean Geographic
 384 Intercalibration Group (European Commission, 2018). The relationship between EQR_{Chl-a} and
 385 nutrient concentrations was not statistically significant for WT IIIW, so the G/M boundary for
 386 TP (expressed as geometric mean) was chosen according to Giovanardi et al. (2018), while
 387 G/M boundary DIN was derived from the relationship between log DIN and log TP. The G/M
 388 boundaries in the WT IIIE were derived using the statistical toolkit by Phillips et al. (2018) for
 389 TP and DIN, whereas for PO_4 and bottom DO they were derived from probability curves.

390 The derived boundary for the concentration of DIN for WT IIA are 34% lower than the
 391 thresholds established for nitrates in French waters; WT IIIW is $1.61 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, which is 60 %
 392 higher than the threshold $1 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ established for nitrates in Greek waters (Table 1) but well
 393 below to the assessment boundary of $8.7 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ used by Lefebvre and Devreker (2020) for
 394 the French offshore Mediterranean waters (Giovanardi et al., 2018; Salas Herrero et al., 2019;
 395 Lefebvre and Devreker, 2020).

396

397

398 Table 6: Values for each criteria element and Water Type (WT), corresponding to different quantiles (in bold) of the area under the curve of the
 399 related Probability Density Function. Note: the negative concentration values, when occurred for lower limits of some parameters, have been
 400 reported as zero.

Criteria elements	Units	Water Type	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.5 (median)	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.95	0.99
Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	WT I	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.77	2.25	8.74	23.44	34.03	44.57	48.85	51.43
		WT IIA	0.05	0.27	0.47	0.85	1.27	2.36	4.17	5.74	8.61	11.56	17.83
		WT IIIW	0.00	0.39	0.64	0.94	1.19	1.69	2.42	3.02	4.17	5.50	9.41
		WT IIIE	0.10	0.13	0.17	0.26	0.37	0.71	1.37	2.00	3.19	4.36	6.44
Total Phosphorus	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	WT I	0.05	0.09	0.13	0.20	0.26	0.41	0.60	0.74	0.93	1.09	1.33
		WT IIA	0.00	0.08	0.13	0.17	0.19	0.22	0.30	0.37	0.56	0.86	2.12
		WT IIIW	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.16	0.18	0.24	0.36	0.48	0.75	1.13	2.57
		WT IIIE	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.13	0.19	0.23	0.30	0.38	0.58
Dissolved Oxygen Bottom	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	WT I	77	101	120	146	167	201	233	249	267	278	291
		WT II	99	157	180	203	217	236	254	264	278	290	317
		WT IIIW	193	205	211	219	226	237	250	258	270	281	303
		WT IIIE	0	33	127	181	199	214	221	224	232	243	304
Secchi disk	m	WT I	0.88	1.20	1.48	1.97	2.46	3.6	5.28	6.56	8.64	10.54	14.10
		WT IIA	1.31	2.53	3.32	4.41	5.31	7.03	9.10	10.55	12.84	15.02	19.94
		WT IIIW	2.85	4.85	6.42	8.88	11.01	15.00	19.11	21.41	24.17	26.00	28.38
		WT IIIE	0.27	1.89	3.13	5.04	6.70	9.87	13.32	15.37	17.98	19.85	22.52
Chlorophyll a	$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	WT I	0.01	0.15	0.28	0.44	0.61	1.1	2.14	3.31	6.22	10.61	29.47
		WT IIA	0.08	0.13	0.18	0.25	0.33	0.50	0.76	0.98	1.38	1.80	2.89
		WT IIIW	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.08	0.10	0.15	0.22	0.27	0.37	0.47	0.75
		WT IIIE	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.13	0.16	0.27	0.48	0.68	1.11	1.69	3.62
Phosphate	$\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$	WT IIIE	0	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.09	0.16	0.27	0.71

401

402 Figure 5: Cumulative distribution curves for Chl-a, dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), total
 403 phosphorus (TP), Secchi disk depth and dissolved oxygen in bottom waters for the different
 404 water types in the Adriatic Sea.

405 For WT IIIE, although nutrient and Chl-a concentrations did not seem to have a good linear
 406 relationship, the boundary values obtained with the two methodological approaches were
 407 quite comparable, so we came to threshold values: $0.16 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for PO_4 ; $0.33 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for TP
 408 and $2.11 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for DIN (Table 7), which are also comparable to those defined using the
 409 toolkit developed by Phillips et al. (2018). In that work, data from the Greek coastal areas for
 410 the period 2012-2015 were used (annual data including spring and autumn sampling periods).
 411 The application of the toolkit in 2018 (Pavlidou et al., 2019) had resulted in the following
 412 thresholds: $0.082 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for PO_4 , rounding to $0.1 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for G/M with regression model 1
 413 ($r=-0.51$; $R^2=0.26$); $0.28 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ rounded to $0.30 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for TP ($r=-0.636$; $R^2=0.41$) and 1.73
 414 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for NO_3 ($r=-0.334$; $R^2=0.11$), which was finally set at $1.00 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, taking into account
 415 our knowledge of the area and also setting a strict G/M value (Pavlidou et al., 2019).

416

417 Figure 6: Cumulative distribution curves for PO₄, total phosphorus (TP), dissolved inorganic
 418 nitrogen (DIN), and dissolved oxygen in bottom waters for Water Type (WT) IIIE in Saronikos
 419 Gulf.

420 The threshold values derived for concentration of TP is 0.66 μmol L⁻¹ for WT I and 0.42 μmol
 421 L⁻¹ for WT IIA, the latter value being lower than the value of 0.58 μmol L⁻¹ estimated by Salas
 422 Herrero et al. (2019) for MED IIA Adriatic Sea (IT), but close to the G/M boundary of 0.48
 423 calculated by Giovanardi et al. (2018). One of the main differences with Salas Herrero et al.
 424 (2019) is that we used the annual geometric mean to smooth the effects of extreme values,
 425 rather than the individual values collected during annual monitoring.

426 Since the hypoxic events in the northern Adriatic and Saronikos Gulf (Elefsis Bay) are seasonal
 427 (Alvisi and Cozzi, 2016; Pavlidou et al., 2019; Kralj et al., 2019) and often last only a few weeks,
 428 the 10th percentile of the bottom concentration measured during the warm stratification
 429 period (June to November) was chosen as boundary for dissolved oxygen. A similar approach
 430 was used by Lefebvre and Devreker (2020) for French coastal waters. These boundaries were
 431 derived for each Water Type from the cumulative probability distribution curves generated
 432 according to the method proposed by Giovanardi et al. (2006). The cumulative probability
 433 distributions for DO in bottom waters show that the three water types are well differentiated
 434 at the 10th percentile while at the 50th percentile there is no differentiation between WT IIA
 435 and WT IIIW (Figure 5). At the 10th percentile the boundaries were 134 μmol L⁻¹ (3 mL L⁻¹), 180

436 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ (4 mL L^{-1}) and $211 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ (5 mL L^{-1}) and $127 (2.8 \text{ mL L}^{-1})$ for WT I, WT IIA and WT IIIW
437 and IIIE, respectively (Table 7).

438 Transparency is measured in most monitoring programs (Sandén and Hakansson, 1996; Devlin
439 et al., 2008; Simboura et al., 2014; Pavlidou et al., 2015) as the depth of Secchi disk
440 disappearance (Secchi, 1864; Cialdi and Secchi, 1865). It is a rough approximation of water
441 transparency because it directly detects changes in the visible light field (Preisendorfer, 1986).
442 Increased nutrient loading often leads to an increase in phytoplankton biomass in the water
443 column and reduces the transparency. Measurements of Secchi disk depth have been carried
444 out in different regions (Justic, 1988; Gallegos et al., 2011; Fleming-Lehtinen and Lamanenn,
445 2012) providing many long-term data series that are valuable for understanding
446 environmental changes caused by increasing anthropogenic pressures, such as evidence for
447 the evolution of phytoplankton biomass in response to eutrophication (Sandén and
448 Hakansson, 1996; HELCOM 2009; Fleming-Lehtinen and Laamanen, 2012). Although the
449 Secchi disk is a reliable tool in offshore waters, the measurement can have significant error in
450 shallow coastal waters due to sediment resuspension and terrestrial inputs. Secchi disk depth
451 for oligotrophic waters in the Eastern Mediterranean varies between 20 and 40 m (Ignatiades
452 et al., 1995); however, in the eutrophic NW Adriatic Sea (e.g. Emilia Romagna), Secchi disk
453 depth is lower (max 3.2 m; Giovanardi et al., 2006). According to Karydis (2009), Secchi depths
454 between 10 and 20 m characterize mesotrophic conditions while Secchi disk depth for
455 eutrophic waters is less than 10 m. The contribution of riverine suspended matter and
456 resuspended sediments decreases from near shore to offshore waters, so the boundary was
457 derived from the relationship between transparency and Chl-a, when significant. As can be
458 seen from the cumulative probability plots of Secchi disk depth (Figure 3), the Water Types
459 can be readily distinguished. However, it was preferred to derive the boundary from the log-
460 log relationship between Secchi disk depth and water column average Chl-a concentration
461 (averaged down to the depth closest to the Secchi disk depth).

462 Table 7: Metric and Good/Moderate thresholds for the Water Types (WT) in the Adriatic and Aegean Seas proposed by this study, for each criterion within
 463 Descriptor D5. S is the salinity.

Criteria Elements	D5C1 Nutrients in the Water Column			D5C2 Chlorophyll-a ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	D5C4 Transparency Secchi Disk (m)	D5C5 Dissolved Oxygen in the bottom of the water ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)
	DIN ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)	TP ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)	PO ₄ ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			
WT I (S<34.5) Type I (IT)	15.6	0.66		5.00	3.0	134
WT II (34.5<S<37.5) Type IIA Adriatic	6.85	0.42		1.50	5.0	180
WT III (S>37.5) Type IIIW (IT, HR)	1.61	0.26		0.64	9.0	211
WT III (S>37.5) Type IIIE (GR)	2.11	0.33	0.16	0.53	6.6	127

464

465 The Chl-a concentrations along the water column were averaged from surface to the depth
466 closest to the Secchi disk depth (SD), as mentioned above. From the Chl-a boundaries given in
467 Table 7, the boundaries for Secchi Disk were derived according to the equation $\log SD^{-1}=a + b \log$
468 Chl-a (Table S5) and resulted in the following values: 3 m for WT I, 5 m for WT IIA, 9 m for WT
469 IIIW and 6.6 for WT IIIE. The 10-percentile values resulting from the cumulative curves would be
470 1.5, 3.3, and 6.4 m for WT I, WT II and WT IIIW, respectively, while the 50-percentile values would
471 be 3.6, 7.0, and 15.0 m for WT I, WT II, and WT IIIW, respectively. Therefore, the values derived
472 for the $\log SD^{-1}$ - \log Chl-a relationships represent intermediate percentiles.

473 In addition to the threshold values for each WT of the two case studies, the worst and reference
474 conditions have also been defined from different sources (Table 8), which have been used in the
475 application of NEAT.

476

477 **3.2 Aggregation and integration methods for GES evaluation: NEAT application**

478 **3.2.1. Adriatic Sea**

479 The overall score obtained with NEAT weighted for SAU areas, attributing to transparency a
480 weight of 0.5, classifies the Adriatic Sea as a whole in High status with a confidence level of 100%,
481 but very close to the boundary between Good and High class (Table 9). NEAT values for the
482 different SAUs (level 4 from Figure 2) ranged from 0.751 (Emilia Romagna) to 0.917 (Eastern
483 Middle Adriatic-Croatia) with a confidence level between 99.2 and 100% (Table 9). Considering
484 the smallest SAUs (level 5 in Figure 2), the range of the NEAT values was larger (from 0.627 to
485 0.987), with the lowest confidence level of 46.6% (Table S6). The NEAT scores for D5C2 Chl-a
486 show that GES is achieved for each SAU, with a scoring always near 1 that indicates best
487 conditions (Table 9). The data considered for this assessment (see Table 1) fall during a period
488 characterized by declining trend in phytoplankton biomass in the Adriatic Sea, as evidenced by
489 satellite remote sensing (Colella et al., 2016) and in situ measurements in the Long-Term
490 Ecological Research stations in the Gulf of Trieste (Kralj et al., 2019; Cozzi et al., 2020). However,
491 several studies based on different datasets, time periods and observation systems show
492 contrasting results: analyses of temporal variations of Chl-a concentration in northern Adriatic
493 Sea in the period 1971-2015 performed by Grilli et al. (2020) showed no clear

494 Table 8: Ranges (worst condition and reference condition) for the water types (WT) in the sub-areas of the Adriatic Sea and the Saronikos Gulf. SAU: Spatial Assessment
 495 Unit.

SAU	Water types	DIN $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$				TP $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$				Chl a $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$				DO bottom water $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$				Secchi disk depth m			
		Worst condition		Reference condition		Worst condition		Reference condition		Worst condition		Reference condition		Worst condition		Reference condition		Worst condition		Reference condition	
Northern Adriatic	WTI	120.29	1	4.98	3	2.91	2	0.29	3	27.46	1	1.40	5	27	6	262	3	0.5	6	10	9
	WTIIA	68.73	1	1.66	3	2.91	2	0.23	3	11.98	1	0.33	5	50	6	244	3	0.5	6	20	9
	WTIII W	8.18	1	1.41	3	2.6	1	0.23	3	3.91	1	0.34	3	163	6	243	3	3	6	26	1 0
Middle Adriatic	WTI	39.12	2	4.98	3	1.27	2	0.29	3	24.87	4	1.40	5	89	7	262	3	1	8	10	9
	WTIIA	39.12	2	1.66	3	2.60	1	0.23	3	9.30	1	0.33	5	153	6	244	3	0.5	6	20	9
	WTIII W	27.20	1	1.41	3	2.64	1	0.23	3	8	1	0.34	3	189	6	243	3	2	6	26	1 0
Southern Adriatic	WTIII W	7.76	1	1.41	3	2.60	1	0.23	3	3.91	1	0.34	3	163	6	243	3	3	6	26	1 0
Saronikos Gulf	WTIIIE	2.99	1 1	0.46	1 1	0.33	1 1	0.13	1 1	1.80	1 1	0.07	1 1	130	1 2	240	1 1	5.70		14.9	1 1
						PO ₄ $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$															
						0.20	1 1	0.02	1 1												

496

1: max for the WT in the specific sub-area

2: max for WTI and WTIIA in the specific sub-area

3: median from EMODnet chemistry data for the specific WT

4: max from Ninčević et al., 1998

5: from Giovanardi et al., 2018

6: min for the WT in the specific sub-area

7: Marasović et al., 1991

8: from Ninčević -Gladan et al. 2015

9: from Justic, 1988

10: from Buljan and Zore-Armada, 1979

497 11: max from EMODnet chemistry data for the specific WT

498 12: min from EMODnet chemistry data for the specific WT

499 trend, a study covering the period 1971-2007 showed a global trend of decreasing Chl-a in N
500 Adriatic Sea (Mozetič et al., 2010), while a time series of satellite data covering the period 1998-
501 2014 showed a positive trend (Salgado Hernanz et al., 2019). In any case, it should be made clear
502 that phytoplankton biomass in our assessment period was much lower than during the peak of
503 eutrophication in the 1970s and 1980s (Giani et al., 2012; Djakovac et al., 2015; Viaroli et al.,
504 2018), which should explain at least partly the high scores for Chl-a. In addition, a model
505 projection for the entire Adriatic Sea shows that the process of oligotrofication will continue in
506 the future, as recently demonstrated by Mentaschi et al. (2024).

507

508 On the contrary, at the level of criterion D5C1 – nutrients, GES was not reached in three SAUs
509 (aggregation level 4 in Figure 2) of the Adriatic Sea, where the score for TP fell below the G/M
510 boundary (Table 9). All of these were located in two Italian regions in the middle and southern
511 Adriatic, Abruzzo and Apulia. Such a result would be expected in the Gulf of Manfredonia (part
512 of Apulia region, western Southern Adriatic) which is affected by local riverine discharges
513 (Focardi et al., 2009; Campanelli et al., 2013), but not in the southernmost stations of Apulia
514 region. Considering the level 5 of the SAUs (Figure 2), a total of 16 SAUs have a NEAT value for
515 TP below the target value (all 6 in Abruzzo and 10 out of 12 in Apulia region; Table S6).
516 Interestingly, the TP values for the SAUs in Molise region, which is geographically situated
517 between Abruzzo and Apulia regions, were above the NEAT target value. This situation derives
518 by the high TP concentrations in Abruzzo (median value of $1.1 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and should be studied in
519 more detail. In other regions with WT IIA, TP is usually present in low concentrations, as in the
520 case of Marche and Molise regions where the median surface concentrations were 3 to 6-fold
521 lower ($0.17 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and $0.40 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, respectively). Apulian waters are classified as type WT
522 IIIW, but median TP concentrations in Apulia ($0.41 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) are similar to those in Molise, which
523 waters are in type WT IIA. It is worth to note that the Southern Adriatic has a NEAT value similar
524 to the Northern Adriatic and this, in part, could be attributable to the elevated DL for the
525 determination of TP.

526 Regarding the criterion D5C4 - transparency, when to this criterion is given a 0.5 weight as it is a
527 secondary criterion, GES is always achieved, but in 12 SAUs of the Adriatic: 3 in western Northern
528 Adriatic, 6 in the western central Adriatic and 3 in the western Southern Adriatic (in the Gulf of
529 Manfredonia) the NEAT values are below the target value for transparency. Both when to the
530 transparency is given a very low weight (0.001) or the same weight as the other criteria elements
531 (1) the GES is reached in all the SAUs of the Adriatic (Tables S6 and S7). In the latter case,

532 however, the average GES is lower, in particular for western Southern Adriatic (decrease of NEAT
533 value from 0.759 to 0.749) and western Middle Adriatic (decrease of NEAT value from 0.817 to
534 0.749).

535 Considering criterion D5C5, low dissolved oxygen values in bottom waters are observed in
536 different SAUs of the Adriatic Sea. Consequently, GES was not reached in the whole Northern
537 Adriatic (Table 9), specifically in many SAUs of the western Northern Adriatic (3 out of 6 in Veneto
538 and 8 out of 9 in Emilia Romagna) and eastern Northern Adriatic (one out of 5 in Friuli Venezia
539 Giulia, 3 out of 6 in Slovenia and one in Croatia, Table S6). Most of these SAUs are located in the
540 area south of the Po River Delta, but also in the Gulf of Trieste, areas already studied for their
541 characteristic occasional seasonal hypoxia (Djakovac et al., 2015; Kralj et al., 2019). Low oxygen
542 levels associated to non-GES for nutrients and transparency were found also in the Gulf of
543 Manfredonia (Southern Italy-Apulia region; Table S6). It is important to emphasize that even if
544 one or more criteria elements do not reach the target values, the overall NEAT value for those
545 SAUs indicate, however, a good status, influenced by high scores for Chl-a (values close to 1).

546 The decision on how much weight is given to a certain variable in the calculation of NEAT had a
547 major implication on the final NEAT score. In the case of different weighting of the secondary
548 criterion (transparency), 65 % of the 69 smallest SAUs considered were in High status when using
549 the weight of 0.5 (Table S6). The number of SAUs scored as High was lower (49 %) when using
550 weight of 1 and higher (72 %) when giving a negligible weight to transparency (weight 0.001)
551 (Table S6).

552 We compared NEAT results with the TRIX index results (Vollenweider et al., 1998; Tables S5 in
553 supplementary material). If we set a TRIX value of 5 as the boundary between Good and
554 Moderate (Rinaldi and Giovanardi, 2011), the two scores match at the level GES/non-GES for ~98
555 % of the SAUs (Table S6). While all SAUs achieved GES according to NEAT scores, only one SAU
556 in Emilia-Romagna region in the western Northern Adriatic did not reach the GES status
557 according to TRIX (Table S6). TRIX and NEAT (0.001 weighting factor for transparency) scores
558 were inversely correlated ($r = -0.4359$, $p = 0.0002$). If we consider just the four-class classification
559 based on TRIX (High/Good/Moderate/Bad) provided by Giovanardi and Vollenweider (2004), 80
560 % of SAUs would be in High status, 19% in Good status and 1% in Moderate status.

561 The exclusive use of surface data for the criterion D5C2 chlorophyll-a may present a limitation in
562 the GES assessment as, especially for Water Types II and III, Chlorophyll-a maximum is generally
563 not at the surface (Revelante and Gilmartin, 1995; Viličić et al., 2008; Ninčević et al., 2002). A
564 further step should be to evaluate the data integrated over the water column. Therefore, a more

565 robust evaluation of GES requires the establishment of boundaries for a common and
566 harmonized dataset for the Adriatic, characterized by a sufficient amount of data along the water
567 column, to calculate significant statistics of integrated Chlorophyll-a and nutrient data.

568 **3.2.2. Saronikos Gulf**

569 NEAT has already been applied to Saronikos Gulf, using data from 2000-2016, to assess the
570 environmental status in a holistic manner (Pavlidou et al., 2019). In Pavlidou et al. (2019), Psittalia
571 was classified in Moderate status, whereas the inner Saronikos Gulf in Good and the Elefsis Bay
572 in Poor status, revealing mostly eutrophication problems in Elefsis Bay, mainly expressed as
573 phytoplankton bloom. In that work, nitrates and phosphates were used as nutrient criteria
574 elements with target values of $1.00 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and $0.10 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, respectively.

575 According to the results of NEAT of this study, the overall score obtained with NEAT weighted
576 for SAU areas and giving to transparency a weight of 0.5 indicates that the Saronikos Gulf as a
577 whole was classified into High status (with a reliability of 80.4%), while the different SAUs were
578 classified in Good (Psittalia with confidence 83.6%), high (Inner Saronikos, with a reliability of
579 85.8%) and moderate (Elefsis Bay with a reliability of 78.6%) status (Table 10). Elefsis Bay, which
580 was classified as in moderate status, is considered as the most impacted sub-area of Saronikos
581 Gulf (industrial pressures). It appears that the eutrophication problems in Elefsis Bay are mainly
582 associated to phytoplankton blooms, which probably cause low water transparency, given that
583 scores of both Chl-a and transparency indicated Bad status (Table 10). There is an increasing
584 gradient of water quality from Psittalia (good status) towards the Inner (high status), which is
585 related to the spread of the sewage plume from Psittalia into the inner Saronikos Gulf. The status
586 of Psittalia is mainly linked to the Bad status of TP (Table 10). Here, the scores for criteria D5C1
587 (nutrients other than TP) and D5C2 (Chl-a) corresponded to Good status, whereas bottom oxygen
588 (criterion D5C5) was found in High status. The NEAT scores for D5C2 Chl-a showed that for this
589 criterion, GES is achieved for each SAU but not for the Elefsis Bay. However, it should be noted
590 that NEAT scores are strongly dependent on the boundaries set for Chlorophyll a (see Tables 7
591 and 8).

592 Table 9: Results of the NEAT assessment values, for the Adriatic Sea sub areas, weighting by Spatial Assessment Unit (SAU) area and weighting by transparency
 593 (transparency weight, factor: 0.5). NEAT values are displayed as SAUs with ecosystem components and calculated as summarized values. The status class is
 594 marked with different colors: "High" in blue; "Good" in green; "Moderate" in yellow.

595

SAU	Area (km ²)	Bottom Oxygen	Chlorophyll a	DIN	TP	Transparency	NEAT value	Confidence (%)
ADRIATIC	1308.5	0.682	0.965	0.87	0.823	0.677	0.809	100
NORTHERN ADRIATIC (NAd)	637.53	0.589	0.942	0.919	0.928	0.689	0.800	100
Western NAd	303.75	0.497	0.93	0.925	0.880	0.639	0.757	100
Veneto	121.5	0.562	0.883	0.913	0.898	0.660	0.766	100
Emilia Romagna	182.25	0.454	0.961	0.932	0.868	0.625	0.751	99.2
Eastern NAd	333.78	0.673	0.952	0.915	0.973	0.735	0.839	100
Friuli Venezia Giulia	101.25	0.671	0.943	0.769	1.000	0.656	0.808	100
Slovenia	105.65	0.550	0.906	0.978	0.902	0.663	0.781	100
Croatia NAd	126.88	0.778	0.998	0.968	1.000	0.858	0.911	100
MIDDLE ADRIATIC (MAd)	488.76	0.807	0.981	0.861	0.778	0.662	0.840	100
Western MAd	364.5	0.803	0.984	0.822	0.703	0.593	0.813	100
Marche	121.5	0.762	0.960	0.767	0.961	0.450	0.803	99.9
Molise	60.75	0.904	0.987	0.692	0.663	0.667	0.829	100
Abruzzo	121.5	0.814	1.000	0.858	0.530	0.654	0.81	100
Puglia MAd	60.75	0.762	1.000	0.99	0.573	0.681	0.824	99.9
Eastern MAd-Croatia	124.26	0.820	0.972	0.976	0.996	0.865	0.917	100
SOUTHERN ADRIATIC- Western SAd-Puglia	182.25	0.668	1.000	0.714	0.594	0.673	0.759	99.2

596 It seems that the NEAT classification for D5 has made the connection with the pressures clear.
597 Industrial and shipping activities affect the environmental quality of Elefsis Bay, a small and
598 shallow almost enclosed bay. Elefsis Bay differs from the rest of the Saronikos Gulf not only for
599 its morphology, but also for the extent of pollution it experiences. The hydrological conditions of
600 Elefsis Bay, with low freshwater inflows and limited water exchange, result in strong seasonal
601 density stratification of the water mass, leading to hypoxia and anoxia that last for about five
602 months. Under these conditions, nutrients and organic matter are retained within the bay,
603 leading to high nutrient enrichment (Pavlidou et al., 2013).

604 With regard to criteria D5C4 (transparency) and D5C1 (nutrients), our results indicate that low
605 transparency and high TP characterize Elefsis Bay and the Psitallia sewage effluent, respectively.
606 Thus, phytoplankton blooms and low transparency values are associated to non-GES in Elefsis
607 Bay.

608 It is noteworthy that there is a shift in the status of the sub-areas in this study, when compared
609 to the findings of Pavlidou et al. (2019), since in the present work more criteria elements and
610 different target, worst and reference values were used. The latter confirms the hypothesis that
611 in the NEAT assessment, the use of different indicators could probably change the overall
612 assessment towards better or worse status (Uusitalo et al., 2016).

613 The comparison between results obtained from NEAT and those from TRIX index (Vollenweider
614 et al., 1998; Tables S7 and S8 in supplementary material) confirmed that NEAT allows to better
615 recognize the well - known pressure gradients in the study area (e.g. WWTP), including the spatial
616 gradients from the pressure source. However, for the Saronikos Gulf, the two methods agreed
617 at the level GES/no-GES for 75% of the SAUs (Tables S8 and S9).

618 We tried to compare our results with those of Frascchetti et al (2022), who assessed the GES in
619 MPAs and buffer zone in the Mediterranean Sea based on ecological indicators (*P. oceanica*,
620 Canopy algae, Erect algae, Turf, Barren, Sea urchins, and Fish). The assessment carried out by
621 these authors using NEAT showed that the GES in the Adriatic and Aegean Sea is Moderate. As
622 this study considered an area close to the coast it is expected that human impacts are greater
623 compared to areas further offshore that are monitored under the MSFD.

624 Table 10: Results of the NEAT assessment values, for the Saronikos Gulf, weighting by Spatial Assessment Unit (SAU) area and weighting by transparency
 625 (transparency weight, factor: 0.5). NEAT values are displayed as SAUs with ecosystem components and calculated as summarized values. The status class is
 626 marked with different colors: "high" in blue; "good" in green; "moderate" in yellow; "bad" in red.

SAU	Area (km ²)	Bottom Oxygen	Chlorophyll a	DIN	Phosphate	TP	Transparency	NEAT value	Confidence (%) ⁶²⁷ ₆₂₈
SARONIKOS GULF	2973.9	0.888	0.728	0.819	0.843	0.752	0.804	0.803	80.4
Psittalia	64.96	0.943	0.703	0.688	0.611	0.000	0.836	0.683	83.6
Inner Saronikos	416.99	0.903	0.838	0.845	0.863	0.859	0.937	0.876	83.8
Elefsis Bay	71.48	0.747	0.113	0.786	0.934	0.812	0.000	0.485	78.6

629 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

630 In this work, a combination of different methodological approaches was used to establish
631 thresholds for nutrients DIN and phosphates, (phosphates only for the case of Saronikos Gulf),
632 TP, Chl-a, transparency (expressed as Secchi disk depth) and dissolved oxygen in the bottom
633 waters, within the framework of MSFD criteria and criteria elements for Descriptor 5
634 (Eutrophication). This is one of the first attempts to set common methodologies and
635 methodological standards for eutrophication assessment at sub-basin scale in the
636 Mediterranean Sea, which is essential in marine environments shared by many countries. The
637 aim was to propose common criteria elements and metrics that can be used for a harmonized
638 assessment of environmental status, at basin scale. To this end, we established G/M thresholds
639 for four Water Types (I, II, IIIW, IIIE) based on datasets provided by Italy, Slovenia, Croatia and
640 Greece for the period 2010 - 2018. The criteria elements selected in this work were the same for
641 all countries, which supports a consistent approach to the GES assessment in the Eastern
642 Mediterranean. The comparison of NEAT with TRIX showed good comparability, with the
643 advantage that NEAT makes it possible to determine which of the criterion elements deviate
644 most from GES and it allows aggregation at different spatial levels.

645 The adoption of laboratory methods with common detection limits is a critical aspect, especially
646 for phosphorus, which is present in much lower concentrations than dissolved inorganic nitrogen
647 in the Mediterranean waters. Lower detection limits would be advisable to allow quantification
648 of concentrations in a larger number of water samples.

649 In the Adriatic Sea, nutrient input into coastal waters is characterized by strong short-term,
650 interannual and multidecadal variability. Therefore, no specific time period (e.g. specific months)
651 and no specific frequency for sampling can be proposed for the entire marine area. A
652 representative annual value requires at least a seasonal distribution of monitoring, while
653 monthly monitoring would be necessary for a better assessment, especially in areas under the
654 influence of variable river discharges.

655 Regarding the spatial coverage, we considered the smallest SAUs corresponding to the
656 monitoring stations in the Adriatic Sea, since the spatial distribution of the monitoring stations
657 limited the interpolation for a larger spatial coverage. In fact, the distance between contiguous
658 transects in the western Adriatic is 26 miles, which in some areas is insufficient to account for
659 the pronounced horizontal gradients typical of the northern Adriatic, especially due to the large
660 inputs from rivers. A higher spatial resolution should be considered to ensure that local effects

661 remain recognizable. The spatial horizontal scale could be extended by satellite data products
662 for Chl-a and transparency, while nutrients could be derived by biogeochemical models
663 assimilating data from regional monitoring. In this work we tested whether NEAT can be used as
664 a common methodology for GES assessment. NEAT has proven to be a useful tool for integrated
665 assessment but is highly dependent on: a) the definition of reference and worst conditions and
666 thresholds for G/M and b) the ecosystem components and criteria elements used. According to
667 Borja et al. (2019), in most cases a number of indicators between 20 and 40 could be sufficient
668 to significantly assess the state of the environment using NEAT. However, this number has been
669 tested for several or all 11 descriptors of the MSFD, but not for a single one, as in this case for
670 Descriptor 5. For D5 in particular, the use of multiple MSFD criteria elements is important to
671 obtain a more comprehensive assessment of the different pressures affecting the trophic status
672 of marine ecosystems. For a more comprehensive assessment, not only nutrient data, but also
673 other criteria elements of D5 of the MSFD that show eutrophication effects are needed.

674 In this work we have developed a common methodology for the determination of eutrophication
675 thresholds and reference values for the Eastern Mediterranean basin. We have also tested and
676 proposed an integrative tool as a common assessment method for eutrophication status. The
677 establishment of thresholds is closely linked to the need for long-term data and its quality
678 assurance. We found that availability of data obtained with similar monitoring plans is important
679 in all countries, which underlies the need for enhanced monitoring measures also for other
680 ecosystem components, taking an integrated perspective.

681

682 **5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

683 This research received funding from the European Commission DG Environment project
684 MEDREGION: Support Mediterranean Member States towards implementation of the MSFD new
685 GES Decision and programs of measures and contribute to regional/subregional cooperation,
686 under grant agreement n° 11.0661/2018/794286/SUB/ENV.C2. JF was financially supported also
687 by the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (research core funding no. P1-0237). AB and
688 IM were supported during the writing process by GES4SEAS project, funded by the Horizon
689 Europe program (grant agreement no. 101059877). We are very grateful to dr. Franco Giovanardi
690 for the discussion on the statistical approaches.

691 **6. REFERENCES**

692 Andersen J. H., Carstensen J., Conley D. J., Dromph K., Fleming-Lehtinen V., Gustafsson B. G.,
693 Josefson A. B., Norkko A., Villnäs A., Murray C. 2017. Long-term temporal and spatial trends
694 in eutrophication status of the Baltic Sea. *Biological Reviews*, 9: 135-149.

695 Alvisi F., Cozzi S., 2016. Seasonal dynamics and long-term trend of hypoxia in the coastal zone of
696 Emilia Romagna (NW Adriatic Sea, Italy). *Sci. Total Environ*, 541: 1448-146.

697 Barth A., Buga L., Fryber, L., Gatti J., Giorgetti A., Giorg, G., Iona S., Larse, M., Lipizer M., Schaap
698 D., Schlitzer R., Vinci M., Watelet S., Wnzer M. 2015. EMODnet Thematic Lot n° 4 – Chemistry
699 - Methodology for Data QA/QC and DIVA Products. [http://dx.doi.org/10.6092/9f75ad8a-](http://dx.doi.org/10.6092/9f75ad8a-ca32-4a72-bf69-167119b2cc12)
700 [ca32-4a72-bf69-167119b2cc12](http://dx.doi.org/10.6092/9f75ad8a-ca32-4a72-bf69-167119b2cc12).

701 Batistić M., Viličić D., Kovačević V., Jasprica N., R. Garić, Lavigne H., Carić M. 2019. Occurrence of
702 winter phytoplankton bloom in the open southern Adriatic: Relationship with hydroclimatic
703 events in the Eastern Mediterranean. *Continental Shelf Research* 174: 12-25.

704 Bob Wheeler 2020. SuppDists: Supplementary Distributions. R package version 1.1-9.5.
705 <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=SuppDists>.

706 Borja, Á., Galparsoro, I., Irigoien, X., Iriondo, A., Menchaca, I., Muxika, I., Pascual, M., Quincoces,
707 I., Revilla, M., Germán Rodríguez, J., Santurtún, M., Solaun, O., Uriarte, A., Valencia, V., Zorita,
708 I., 2011. Implementation of the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive: a
709 methodological approach for the assessment of environmental status, from the Basque
710 Country (Bay of Biscay). *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 62, 889–904.

711 Borja, Á., Dauer, D.M., Grémare, A., 2012. The importance of setting targets and reference
712 conditions in assessing marine ecosystem quality. *Ecol. Indic.* 12, 1–7.

713 Borja A., Elliott M., Andersen J.H., Berg T., Carstensen J., Halpern S., Heiskanen A.-S., Korpinen,
714 S., Stewart Lowndes J. S., Martin G.; Rodríguez-Espeleta N. Overview of integrative
715 assessment of marine systems: the ecosystem approach in practice. 2016. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 3,
716 20. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2016.00020>.

717 Borja A., Garmendia J. M. Menchaca I., Uriarte A., Sagarmínaga Y. 2019. Yes, We Can! Large-Scale
718 Integrative Assessment of European Regional Seas, Using Open Access Databases. *Frontiers*
719 *in Marine Science*, 6: 10.3389/fmars.2019.00019.

720 Borja A., Menchaca I., Garmendia J.M., Franco J., Larreta J., Sagarmínaga Y., Schembri Y.,
721 González R., Antón R., Micallef T., Camilleri S., Solaun O., Uriarte A., Uyarra M. C. 2021. Big
722 Insights From a Small Country: The Added Value of Integrated Assessment in the Marine
723 Environmental Status Evaluation of Malta. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 8:638232. doi:
724 10.3389/fmars.2021.638232

725 Brush M. J., Mozetič P., Francé J., Bernardi Aubry F., Djakovac T., Faganeli J., Harris L. A., Niesen
726 M. 2021. Phytoplankton Dynamics in a Changing Environment. In: Malone T., Malej A.,
727 Faganeli J., (Eds) *Coastal Ecosystems in Transition: A Comparative Analysis of the Northern*
728 *Adriatic and Chesapeake Bay*, Geophysical Monograph 256: 49-74, 1st Edition, Wiley & Sons
729 Ltd, ISBN: 978-1-119-54358-9.

730 Buga L., Sarbu G., Fryberg F., Wesslander K., Gatti J., Iona S., Tsompanou M., Larsen M.M.,
731 Østrem A.K., Lipizer M., Molina Jack M.E., Giorgetti A. 2021. Quality Control steps for
732 EMODnet Chemistry Eutrophication aggregated datasets - v2021, 10/03/2021, 13 pages,
733 10.6092/4e85717a-a2c9-454d-ba0d-30b89f742713

734 Buljan M., Zore-Armanda M. 1979. Hydrographic properties of the Adriatic Sea in the period from
735 1965 through 1970. *Acta Adriatica* 20:1-368.

736 Cabrini M., Fornasaro D., Cossarini G., Lipizer M., Virgilio D. 2012. Phytoplankton temporal
737 changes in a coastal northern Adriatic site during the last 25 years. *Estuarine Coastal Shelf*
738 *Science* 115: 113-124.

739 Cabrita M. T., Silva A., Oliveira P. B., Angélico M. M., Nogueira M. 2015. Assessing eutrophication
740 in the Portuguese continental Exclusive Economic Zone within the European Marine Strategy
741 Framework Directive. *Ecological Indicators*, 58: 286-299.

742 Campanelli A., Cabrini M., Grilli F., Fornasaro D., Penna P., Kljajić Z., Marini M. 2013. Physical,
743 Biochemical and Biological Characterization of Two Opposite Areas in the Southern Adriatic
744 Sea (Mediterranean Sea) *Open Journal of Marine Science* 3, [DOI:10.4236/ojms.2013.32013](https://doi.org/10.4236/ojms.2013.32013)
745 Carstensen J., Andersen J. H., Gustafsson B. G., Conley D. J. 2014. Deoxygenation of the Baltic
746 Sea during the last century. *Proceedings of the Natural Academy of Science* 111: 15628–5633.
747 Cerino F., Fornasaro D., Kralj M., Giani M., Cabrini M. 2019. Phytoplankton temporal dynamics in
748 the coastal waters of the north-eastern Adriatic Sea. *Nature Conservation* 34: 343–372.
749 Cialdi A., Secchi A. 1865. Sur la transparence de la mer” *Comptes rendus hebdomadaire de*
750 *séances de l’Academie des Sciences* 61: 100-104.
751 Colella S., Falcini F., Rinaldi E., Sammartino M., Santoleri R. 2016. Mediterranean Ocean Colour
752 Chlorophyll Trends. *PLoS ONE* 11(6): e0155756. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0155756.
753 Cozzi S., Cabrini M., Kralj M, De Vittor C., Celio M., Giani M. 2020. Climatic and Anthropogenic
754 Impacts on Environmental Conditions and Phytoplankton Community in the Gulf of Trieste
755 (Northern Adriatic Sea). *Water* 12, 2652; doi:10.3390/w12092652
756 Doncheva V., Hristova O., Dzhurova B. 2018. Thresholds for Eutrophication Indicators in the
757 Bulgarian Black Sea Coastal Zone, *Analytical Chemistry* 72: 891-896.
758 Devlin M. J., Barry J., Mills D.K., Gowen R.J., Foden J., Siveyer D., Tett P. 2008. Relationships
759 between suspended particulate material, light attenuation and Secchi depth in UK marine
760 waters. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 79: 429-439.
761 Djakovic T., Supic, N., Bernardi Aubry, F., Degobbis, D., Giani, M., 2015. Mechanisms of hypoxia
762 frequency changes in the northern Adriatic Sea during the period 1972-2012, 2015. *J. Mar.*
763 *Syst.* 141, 179–189.
764 D’Ortenzio F., Ribera d’Alcalà M. 2009. On the trophic regimes of the Mediterranean Sea: a
765 satellite analysis. *Biogosciences* 6: 139-148.
766 Emeis K.- C., van Beusekom J., Callies U., Ebinghaus R., Kannen A., Kraus G., Kröncke I., Lenhart
767 H., Lorkowski I., Matthias V., Möllmann C., Pätsch J., Scharfe M., Thomas H., Weisse R., Zorita
768 E. 2015. The North Sea—A shelf sea in the Anthropocene *Journal Marine System* 141:18-33.
769 EMODnet Chemistry 2021. Mediterranean Sea - Eutrophication and Acidity aggregated datasets
770 1911/2020 v2021. <https://doi.org/10.6092/ep6n-tp63>
771 European Commission. 1991a. Council Directive 91/676/EEC of 12 December 1991 concerning
772 the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources.
773 *Off.J.Eur.Communities* L375: 1-8.
774 European Commission. 1991b. Council Directive 91/271/EEC of 21 May 1991 concerning urban
775 waste-water treatment. *Off.J.Eur.Communities*, L135: 40-52.
776 European Commission. 2000. Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the
777 Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of
778 water policy. *Off.J.Eur.Union* L327: 1–72.
779 European Commission, 2008. Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the
780 Council establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental
781 policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive). *Official Journal of the European Union*, L164:
782 19-40.
783 European Commission. 2009. Guidance Document on Eutrophication Assessment in the
784 Context of European Water Policies. Common Implementation Strategy Guidance Document
785 No. 23. Luxembourg: Office for Official Publications of the European Union.
786 European Commission. 2017a. Commission Decision (EU) 2017/848 of 17 May 2017 laying down
787 criteria and methodological standards on good environmental status of marine waters and
788 specifications and standardised methods for monitoring and assessment, and repealing
789 Decision 2010/477/EU.
790 European Commission. 2017b. Commission Directive (EU) 2017/845 of 17 May 2017 amending
791 Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the indicative
792 lists of elements to be taken into account for the preparation of marine strategies.

793 European Commission. 2018. Commission Decision (EU) 2018/229 of 12 February 2018
794 establishing, pursuant to Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the
795 Council, the values of the Member State monitoring system classifications as a result of the
796 intercalibration exercise and repealing Commission Decision 2013/480/EU.
797 European Environmental Agency. 2019. Oxygen concentrations in coastal and marine waters.
798 Copenhagen, 33 pp.

799 Ferreira, J. G., J. H. Andersen, A. Borja, S. B. Bricker, J. Camp, M. Cardoso da Silva, E. Garcés, A.-
800 S. Heiskanen, C. Humborg, L. Ignatiades, C. Lancelot, A. Menesguen, P. Tett, N. Hoepffner, U.
801 Claussen, 2011. Overview of eutrophication indicators to assess environmental status within
802 the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 93:
803 117-131.

804 Fleming-Lehtinen V., Laamanen M. 2012. Long-term changes in Secchi depth and the role of
805 phytoplankton in explaining light attenuation in the Baltic Sea. *Estuarine Coastal Shelf Science*
806 102–103: 1–10.

807 Focardi S., Specchiulli A., Spagnoli F., Fiesoletti F., Rossi C. 2009. A combined approach to
808 investigate the biochemistry and hydrography of a shallow bay in the South Adriatic Sea: the
809 Gulf of Manfredonia (Italy). *Environmental Monitoring Assessment* 153: 209–220.

810 Frascchetti S., Fabbri E., Tamburello L., Uyarra M. C., Micheli F., Sala E., Pipitone C.,
811 Badalamenti F., Bevilacqua S., Boada J., Cebrian E., Ceccherelli G., Chiantore M., D'Anna G.,
812 Di Franco A., Farina S., Giakoumi S., Gissi E., Guala I., Guidetti P., Katsanevakis S., Manea E.,
813 Montefalcone M., Sini M., Asnaghi V., Calò A., Di Lorenzo M., Garrabou J., Musco L., Oprandi
814 A., Rilov G., Borja A. 2022. An integrated assessment of the Good Environmental Status of
815 Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 305:
816 114370.

817 Gallegos C. L., Werdell P. J., McClain C. R. 2011. Long-term changes in light scattering in
818 Chesapeake Bay inferred from Secchi depth, light attenuation, and remote sensing
819 measurements. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 116,
820 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2011JC007160>.

821 Giani M., Djakovac T., Degobbis D., Cozzi S., Solidoro C., Fonda Umani S. 2012. Recent changes in
822 the marine ecosystems of the northern Adriatic Sea. *Estuarine, Coastal Shelf Science*, 115: 1-
823 13.

824 Giorgetti A., Lipizer M., Molina Jack M.E., Holdsworth N., Jensen H.M., Buga L., Sarbu G., Iona A.,
825 Gatti J., Larsen M., Fyrberg L., Østrem A.K., Schlitzer R. 2020. Aggregated and Validated
826 Datasets for the European Seas: The Contribution of EMODnet Chemistry. *Front. Mar. Sci.*
827 7:583657. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2020.583657.

828 Giovanardi F., Finoia M. G., Russo S., Amori M., Di Lorenzo B. 2006. Coastal waters monitoring
829 data: frequency distributions of the principal water quality variable. *Journal of Limnology*
830 65(2): 65-82.

831 Giovanardi F., Francé J., Mozetič P., Precali R. 2018. Development of ecological classification
832 criteria for the Biological Quality Element phytoplankton for Adriatic and Tyrrhenian coastal
833 waters by means of chlorophyll a (2000/60/EC WFD). *Ecological Indicators* 93: 316-332.

834 Grilli F., Accoroni S., Acri F., Bernardi Aubry F., Bergami C., Cabrini M., Campanelli A., Giani M.,
835 Guicciardi S., Marini M., Neri F., Penna A., Penna P., Pugnetti A., Ravaioli M., Riminucci F.,
836 Ricci F., Totti C., Viaroli P., Cozzi S. 2020. Seasonal and interannual trends of oceanographic
837 parameters over 40 years in the northern Adriatic Sea in relation to nutrient loadings from
838 EMODnet Chemistry data portal. *Water*, 12(8): 2280, Doi: 10.3390/w12082280.

839 Harvey E.T., Walve J., Andersson A., Karlson B. Kratzer S. 2019. The Effect of Optical Properties
840 on Secchi Depth and Implications for Eutrophication Management. *Frontiers in Marine*
841 *Science* 5:496. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2018.00496.HCMR/HNODC 2021. Mediterranean Sea -
842 Eutrophication and Acidity aggregated datasets 1911/2020 v2021.
843 <https://doi.org/10.6092/EP6N-TP63>

844 HELCOM. 2007. Baltic Sea Action Plan. HELCOM Ministerial Meeting Krakow. HELCOM. 101 pp.

845 HELCOM. 2009. "Eutrophication in the Baltic Sea – an integrated thematic assessment of the
846 effects of nutrient enrichment and eutrophication in the Baltic Sea Region," in 115B. Baltic
847 Sea Environmental Proceedings (Helsinki: Helsinki Commission, Baltic Marine Environment
848 Protection Commission).

849 HELCOM 2015. Eutrophication Assessment Manual. 64 pp.

850 HELCOM 2018. Helcom Core indicator report. Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen. Dissolved Inorganic
851 Phosphorus. <https://helcom.fi/baltic-sea-trends/indicators/>

852 Hiddink, J. G., S. Valanko, A. J. Delargy, P. D. van Denderen, 2023. Setting thresholds for good
853 ecosystem state in marine seabed systems and beyond. ICES Journal of Marine Science, 80:
854 698-709.

855 Hyytiäinen, K., Huttunen, I., Kotamäki, N. et al., 2024. Good eutrophication status is a challenging
856 goal for coastal waters. *Ambio* 53, 579–591. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-023-01965-7>

857 Ignatiades L., Georgopoulos D., Karydis M. 1995. Description of a phytoplanktonic community of
858 the oligotrophic waters of SE Aegean Sea (Mediterranean), *P.S.Z.I. Mar. Ecol.*, 16, 13-26.

859 Ignatiades L., Karydis M., Vounatsou P. 1992- A possible method for evaluating Oligotrophy and
860 Eutrophication based on nutrient concentrations. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 24(5), 238-243.

861 IOC-UNESCO (2022) State of the Ocean Report, Pilot edition. Paris, IOCUNESCO (IOC Technical
862 Series, 173), Paris.

863 IMAP, 2017. Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme of the Mediterranean Sea and
864 Cost Related Assessment Criteria, UNEP, Athens, 52 pp.

865 IPCC, 2022. IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate [H.-O.
866 Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, M. Tignor, E. Poloczanska, K.
867 Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Nicolai, A. Okem, J. Petzold, B. Rama, N.M. Weyer (eds.)].
868 Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA, 755 pp.

869 Johnson, N.L. 1949. Systems of frequency curves generated by methods of translation.
870 *Biometrika*, 36: 149-176.

871 Justic D. 1988. Trend in the Transparency of the northern Adriatic Sea 1911-1982. *Marine
872 Pollution Bulletin* 19: 32-35.

873 Kari E., Kratzer S., Beltrán-Abaunza J. M., Therese Harvey E., Vaičiute D. 2017. Retrieval of
874 suspended particulate matter from turbidity –model development, validation, and
875 application to MERIS data over the Baltic Sea. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 38,
876 1983–2003. doi: 10.1080/01431161.2016.1230289.

877 Karydis M. 1999. Evaluation of the Trophic Levels in Greek Coastal Ecosystems. Univ. of Aegean,
878 Scientific Report, Lesvos Island, Greece.

879 Karydis M. 2009. Eutrophication assessment of coastal waters based on indicators: A literature
880 Review. *Global NEST Journal*, Vol 11(4): 373-390.

881 Kazanidis, G., Orejas, C., Borja, A., Kenchington, E., Henry, L.-A., Callery, O., Carreiro-Silva, M.,
882 Egilsdottir, H., Giacomello, E., Grehan, A., Menot, L., Morato, T., Ragnarsson, S.Á. , Rueda,
883 J.L., Stirling, D., Stratmann, T., van Oevelen, D., Palialexis, A., Johnson, D., Roberts J.M. ,
884 2020. Assessing the environmental status of selected North Atlantic deep-sea ecosystems
885 *Ecol. Indicat.*, 119, Article 106624, 10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106624

886 Kemp W. M., Testa J. M., Conley D. J., Gilbert D., Hagy J. D. 2009. Temporal responses of coastal
887 hypoxia to nutrient loading and physical controls. *Biogeosciences* 6: 2985-3008.

888 Kontoyiannis H. (2010), Observations on the circulation of the Saronikos Gulf: A Mediterranean
889 embayment sea border of Athens, Greece, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 115, C06029,
890 doi:10.1029/2008JC005026

891 Kralj M., Lipizer M., Čermelj B., Celio M., Fabbro, C, Brunetti F., Francé J., Mozetič P., Giani M.
892 2019. Hypoxia and dissolved oxygen trends in the northeastern Adriatic Sea (Gulf of Trieste).
893 Deep-Sea Research II 164: 74-88.

894 Kratzer S., Håkansson B., Sahlin C. 2003. Assessing Secchi and photic zone depth in the Baltic Sea
895 from satellite data. *Ambio*, 32(8): 577–85.

896 Laurila-Pant, M., S. Mäntyniemi, Ö. Östman, J. Olsson, L. Uusitalo, A. Lehikoinen, 2021. A
897 Bayesian approach for assessing the boundary between desirable and undesirable
898 environmental status – An example from a coastal fish indicator in the Baltic Sea. *Ecological*
899 *Indicators*, 120: 106975.

900 Lazzari P., Solidoro C., Salon S., Bolzon G. 2016. Spatial variability of phosphate and nitrate in the
901 Mediterranean Sea: A modeling approach. *Deep-Sea Research I*, 108: 39-52.

902 Lefebvre A., Devreker D. 2020. First Comprehensive Quantitative Multi-Parameter Assessment
903 of the Eutrophication Status from Coastal to Marine French Waters in the English Channel,
904 the Celtic Sea, the Bay of Biscay, and the Mediterranean Sea. *Journal of Marine Science and*
905 *Engineering* 8: 561; doi:10.3390/jmse8080561.

906 Lipizer M., Molina Jack M. E., Wesslander K., Fyrberg L., Tsompanou M., Iona A., Buga L., Sarbu
907 G., Gatti J., Larsen M. M., Giorgetti A. 2023 EMODnet Chemistry Regional sea eutrophication
908 data collection and Quality Control loop. Pp. 39, doi: 10.13120/8XM0-5M67

909 Malone T.C., Newton A. 2020. The Globalization of Cultural Eutrophication in the Coastal Ocean:
910 Causes and Consequences. *Frontiers in Marine Sciences* 7:670. doi:
911 10.3389/fmars.2020.00670

912 Menchaca, I., Borja, A., Galparsoro, I., Franco, J., Uyarra, M.C., Uriarte, A., Chust, G., Ibaibarriaga,
913 L. , Bald, J., 2022. Multi-source and multi-scale data integration for the assessment of the
914 marine environmental status of the Basque Coast (SE Bay of Biscay) Estuar. *Coast. Shelf Sci.*,
915 277, Article 108055, 10.1016/j.ecss.2022.108055

916 Mentaschi L, Lovato T, Butenschön on M, Alessandri J, Aragao L, Verri G, Guerra R, Coppini G and
917 Pinardi N (2024) Projected climate oligotrophication of the Adriatic marine ecosystems.
918 *Front. Clim.* 6:1338374. doi: 10.3389/fclim.2024.1338374

919 Mangoni O., Lombardo R., Camminatiello I. Margiotta F., Passarelli A., Saggiomo M. 2017.
920 Phytoplankton community to assess the environmental status of the Adriatic Sea via non-
921 linear partial least squares regression. *Qual Quant* 51, 799–812.
922 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-016-0440-0>

923 Marasović I., Gačić M., Kovačević V., Krstulović N., Kušpilić G., Pucher-Petković T., Odžak N., Šolić
924 M. 1991 Development of the red tide in the Kaštela Bay (Adriatic Sea) *Marine Chemistry* 32:
925 375-387.

926 McCrackin, M. L., Jones, H. P., Jones, P. C., and Moreno-Mateos, D. (2017). Recovery of lakes and
927 coastal marine ecosystems from eutrophication: a global meta-analysis. *Limnol. Oceanogr.*
928 62, 507–518. doi: 10.1002/lno.10441

929 MEDAR Group (The), 2001. Medar-Medatlas Protocol (Version 3) Part I: Exchange Format and
930 Quality Checks for Observed Profiles; *Rap. Int. IFREMER/TMSI/IDM/SIS002-006*, 50 pp.

931 Megard R.O., Berman T. 1989. Effects of algae on the Secchi transparency of the southeastern
932 Mediterranean Sea. *Limnology and Oceanography* 34(8): 1640-1655.

933 Mozetič P., Solidoro C., Cossarini G., Socal G., Precali R., France J., Bianchi F., De Vittor C.,
934 Smolaka N., Fonda Umani S. 2010. Recent trends towards oligotrophication of the northern
935 Adriatic: evidence from chlorophyll a time series. *Estuar. Coasts* 33, 362-375,
936 doi:10.1007/s12237-009-9191-7.

937 Murray C.J., Müller-Karulis B., Carstensen J., Conley D.J., Gustafsson B.G., Andersen J.H. 2019.
938 Past, Present and Future Eutrophication Status of the Baltic Sea. *Frontiers in Marine Science*
939 6:2. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2019.00002.

940 Nemati H., Shokri M.R., Ramezanpour Z., Ebrahimi Pour G.H., Muxika I., Borja Á., 2017. Using
941 multiple indicators to assess the environmental status in impacted and non-impacted bathing
942 waters in the Iranian Caspian Sea. *Ecol. Ind.* 82: 175-182.

943 Nielsen S. L., Sand-Jensen K., Borum J., Geertz-Hansen O. 2002. Phytoplankton, nutrients, and
944 transparency in danish coastal waters. *Estuaries* 25: 930–937. doi: 10.1007/BF02691341

945 Ninčević Z., Marasović I. 1998. Chlorophyll and primary production of size fractionates
946 phytoplankton in the Middle Adriatic Sea *Rapp. Comm. Mer Médit.* 35: 472.

947 Ninčević Ž., Marasović I., Kušpilić G. 2002. Deep chlorophyll-a maximum at one station in the
948 middle Adriatic Sea *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom*, 82:
949 9 – 19.

950 Ninčević-Gladan Z., Bužančić M., Kušpilić G., Grbeć B., Matijević S., Skejić S., Marasović I., Morović
951 M. 2015. The response of phytoplankton community to anthropogenic pressure gradient in
952 the coastal waters of the eastern Adriatic Sea. *Ecological Indicators* 56: 106–115.

953 Nixon, S., 2009. Eutrophication and the macroscope. *Hydrobiologia*, 629: 5-19.

954 OSPAR, 2002. Common assessment criteria, their assessment levels and area classification
955 within the comprehensive procedure of the common procedure. OSPAR Commission for the
956 protection of the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic.

957 Patrício, J., Elliott, M., Mazik, K., Papadopoulou, K.-N., Smith, C.J., 2016. DPSIR-two decades of
958 trying to develop a unifying framework for marine environmental management? *Front. Mar.*
959 *Sci.* 3 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2016.00177>.

960 Pavlidou A., Kontoyiannis H., Anagnostou Ch., Siokou-Frangou I., Pagou K., Krasakopoulou E.,
961 Assimakopoulou G., Zervoudaki S., Zeri Ch., Chatzianestis J., Psyllidou-Giouranovits R., 2013.
962 biogeochemical characteristics in the Elefsis bay (Aegean Sea, Eastern Mediterranean) in
963 relation to anoxia and climate changes. In: Yakushev, E.V. (Ed.), *Handbook of Environmental*
964 *Chemistry, Chemical Structure of Pelagic Redox Interfaces: Observation and Modeling*, *Hdb*
965 *Env Chem*, XIV:161–202. Springer-Verlag.

966 Pavlidou A., Simboura N., Rousselaki E., Tsapakis M., Pagou K., Drakopoulou P., Assimakopoulou
967 G., Kontoyiannis H., Panayotidis P. 2015. Methods of eutrophication assessment in the
968 context of the water framework directive: Examples from the Eastern Mediterranean coastal
969 areas. *Cont. Shelf Res.* 108, 156–168.

970 Pavlidou A., Simboura N., Pagou K., Assimakopoulou G., Gerakaris V., Hatzianestis I., Panayotidis
971 P., Pantazi M., Papadopoulou N., Reizopoulou S., Smith C., Triantaphyllou M., Uyarra M. C.,
972 Varkitzi I., Vassilopoulou V., Zeri C., Borja Á. 2019. Using a holistic ecosystem-integrated
973 approach to assess the environmental status of Saronikos Gulf, Eastern Mediterranean.
974 *Ecological Indicators* 96: 336-350.

975 Peñuelas J. Sardans J. 2022. The global nitrogen-phosphorus imbalance. *Science* 375, 266–267.

976 Phillips G., Kelly M., Teixeira H., Salas Herrero M.F., Free G., Leujak W., Lyche Solheim A., Várbrø
977 G., Poikane S. 2018. Best practice for establishing nutrient concentrations to support good
978 ecological status, EUR 29329 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg,
979 ISBN 978-92-79-92907-6, doi:10.2760/123549, JRC112667.

980 Poikane S., Kelly M. G., Salas Herrero F., Pitt J.-A., Jarvie H. P, Claussen U., Leujak W., Solheim A.
981 L., Teixeira H., Phillips G. 2019. Nutrient criteria for surface waters under the European Water
982 Framework Directive: Current state-of-the-art, challenges and future outlook. *Science of the*
983 *Total Environment* 695: 133888.

984 Polimene L., Pinardi N., Zavatarelli M., Colella S. 2006. The Adriatic Sea ecosystem seasonal cycle:
985 Validation of a three-dimensional numerical model. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*
986 111(C3). 10.1029/2005jc003260

987 Preisendorfer R.W. 1986. Secchi disk science: visual optics of natural waters. *Limnology and*
988 *Oceanography* 31: 909-926.

989 Pugnetti A., Armeni M., Camatti E., Crevatin E., Dell'Anno A., Del Negro P., Milandri A., Socal G.,
990 Fonda Umani S., Danovaro R. 2005 Imbalance between phytoplankton production and
991 bacterial carbon demand in relation to mucilage formation in the Northern Adriatic Sea. *Sci*
992 *Total Environ.* 353(1-3): 162-77.

993 R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing,
994 Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>.

995 Revelante N., Gilmartin M. 1995. The relative increase of larger phytoplankton in a subsurface
996 chlorophyll maximum of the northern Adriatic Sea. *Journal of Plankton Research*, 17: 1535–
997 1562.

998 Rinaldi A., Giovanardi F. 2011. Contribution of Richard A. Vollenweider toward understanding
999 eutrophication of the coastal Adriatic Sea, *Aquat. Ecosyst. Health Manag*, 14: 200–203.

1000 Salas Herrero F., Teixeira H., Poikane S. 2019. A Novel Approach for Deriving Nutrient Criteria to
1001 Support Good Ecological Status: Application to Coastal and Transitional Waters and
1002 Indications for Use. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 6:255. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2019.00255.

1003 Sandén P., Håkansson B. 1996. Long-term trends in Secchi depth in the Baltic Sea. *Limnology and*
1004 *Oceanography* 41: 346–51.

1005 Secchi A. 1864. Relazione delle esperienze fatte a bordo della pontificia pirocorvetta Immacolata
1006 Concezione per determinare la trasparenza del mare, *Il Nuovo Cimento*, 20: 205-237.

1007 Simboura N., Panayotidis P., Papathanassiou E. 2005. A synthesis of the biological quality
1008 elements for the implementation of the European Water Framework Directive in the
1009 Mediterranean ecoregion: the case of Saronikos Gulf. *Ecological Indicators* 5: 253–266.

1010 Simboura N., Zenetos A., Pancucci-Papadopoulou M.A. 2014. Benthic community indicators over
1011 a long period of monitoring (2000–2012) of the Saronikos Gulf, Greece, Eastern
1012 Mediterranean. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 186, 3809–3821.

1013 Stock A. 2015. Satellite mapping of Baltic Sea Secchi depth with multiple regression models.
1014 *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation* 40: 55-64.

1015 Tan, I., Atabay, H., Evcen, A., Kurt, G., Taskin, e., Beken, C.P. 2023. Integrated assessment of
1016 eutrophication in the southern Black Sea waters, using the Nested Environmental Status
1017 Assessment Tool. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, Volume 195, 115424.

1018 Tornero Alvarez M.V., Palma M., Boschetti S., Cardoso A.C., Druon J., Kotta M., Louropoulou E.,
1019 Magliozzi C., Palialexis A., Piroddi C., Ruiz-Orejón L.F., Vasilakopoulos P., Vighi M., Hanke G.
1020 2023. Marine Strategy Framework Directive - Review and analysis of EU Member States' 2020
1021 reports on Monitoring Programmes, EUR 31181 EN, Publications Office of the European
1022 Union, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-76-55778-4, doi:10.2760/8457, JRC129363

1023 UNEP 2013. The EcAp Implementation Progress and the draft list of GES and Targets for the
1024 Mediterranean Sea. UNEP(DEPI)/MED WG.377/3: 37 pp.

1025 UNEP 2019. Agenda Item 3: State of Play of Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme
1026 (IMPAP). Implementation with regards to EO5 and EO9, MEDPOL Monitoring programme and
1027 Way Forward. Guidance on Application of Water Typology and related Monitoring and
1028 Assessment Aspects (Draft) UNE/MAP WG.463/Inf.5, Athens, 12 pp.

1029 UNEP 2021. Agenda item 6: Cross-Cutting Issues -The Integration and Aggregation Rules for
1030 IMAP Ecological Objectives 5, 9 and 10 and Assessment Criteria for Contaminants and
1031 Nutrients Assessment Criteria Methodology for IMAP Common Indicator 13: Pilot
1032 Application in Adriatic Sub-region. UNEP/MAP WG.492/11, 11 pp.

1033 United Nations, 2021. The Second World Ocean Assessment. Volume I. United Nations
1034 publication, ISBN: 978-92-1-1-130422- 0: 570 pp.

1035 Van Leeuwen, SM., Lenhart, H-J., Prins, TC., Blauw, A., Desmit, X., Fernand, L., Friedland, R.,
1036 Kerimoglu. O., Lacroix, G., van der Linden, A., Lefebvre, A., van der Molen, J., Plus, M.,
1037 Ruvalcaba Baroni, I., Silva, T., Stegert, C., Troost, TA. and Vilmin, L., 2023. Deriving pre-
1038 eutrophic conditions from an ensemble model approach for the North-West European seas.
1039 *Front. Mar. Sci.* 10:1129951. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2023.1129951

1040 Van Loon, W., G. Hanke, D. Fleet, S. Werner, J. Barry, J. Strand, J. Eriksson, D. Gräwe, M. Schulz,
1041 T. Vlachogianni, M. Press, E. Blidberg, D. Walvoort, 2019. A European Beach Litter Threshold
1042 Value and Assessment Method. European Commission, Joint Research Centre. MSFD
1043 Technical Group on Marine Litter (TG-ML): 29 pp.

1044 Varkitzi I., Francé J., Basset A., Cozzoli F., Stanca E., Zervoudaki S., Giannakourou A.,
1045 Assimakopoulou G., Venetsanopoulou A., Mozetič P., Tinta T., Skejic S., Vidjak O., Cadiou J-
1046 F., Pagou K. 2018. Pelagic habitats in the Mediterranean Sea: A review of Good
1047 Environmental Status (GES) determination for plankton components and identification of
1048 gaps and priority needs to improve coherence for the MSFD implementation. *Ecological*
1049 *Indicators* 95: 203-218.

1050 Vasilakopoulos, P., A. Palialexis, S. T. Boschetti, A. C. Cardoso, J.-N. Druon, C. Konrad, M. Kotta,
1051 C. Magliozzi, M. Palma, C. Piroddi, L. F. Ruiz-Orejón, F. Salas-Herrero, A. Stips, V. Tornero, G.
1052 Hanke, 2022. Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Thresholds for MSFD Criteria: state of
1053 play and next steps. EUR 31131 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg,
1054 2022, ISBN 978-9276-53689-5, doi:10.2760/640026, JRC128344.: 54 pp.

1055 Viaroli P., Soana E., Pecora S., Laini A., Naldi M., Fano E.A., Nizzoli D. 2018. Space and time
1056 variations of watershed N and P budgets and their relationships with reactive N and P
1057 loadings in a heavily impacted river basin (Po river, Northern Italy). *Science of The Total*
1058 *Environment*, 639: 1574–1587.

1059 Viličić D., Orlić M., Jasprica N. 2008. The deep chlorophyll maximum in the coastal north eastern
1060 Adriatic Sea, *Acta Bot. Croat.* 67 (1): 33–43.

1061 Vinci M., Giorgetti A., Lipizer M. 2017. The role of EMODnet Chemistry in the European challenge
1062 for good environmental status. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 17, 197–204. doi:
1063 10.5194/nhess-17-197-2017.

1064 Vollenweider R.A., Giovanardi F., Montanari G., Rinaldi A., 1998. Characterization of the trophic
1065 conditions of marine coastal waters with special reference to the NW Adriatic Sea. Proposal
1066 for a trophic scale, turbidity and a generalized water quality index. *Environmetrics* 9, 329–
1067 357.

1068 Wasmund N., Kownacka J., Göbel J., Jaanus A., Johansen M., Jurgensone I., Lehtinen S., Powilleit
1069 M. 2017. The Diatom/Dinoflagellate Index as an Indicator of Ecosystem Changes in the Baltic
1070 Sea 1. Principle and Handling Instruction. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 4:22. doi:
1071 10.3389/fmars.2017.00022

1072 Werner, S., E. Fischer, D. Fleet, F. Galgani, G. Hanke, S. Kinsey, M. Mattidi, 2020. Threshold Values
1073 for Marine Litter. EUR 30018 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg,
1074 2020, ISBN 978-92-76-14179-2, doi:10.2760/192427, JRC114131: 27 pp

1075
1076
1077